

D5.9
FIRST PROGRESS REPORT
ON BROADENING IN
EIGHT BROADENING
CITY-REGIONS

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Annex	59	Added Annex 1 to provide context on selection of Broadening city-regions

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2. ABOUT THE REPORT

This report is one of the two progress reports (D5.9 and D5.12) that document key outcomes of the FoodCLIC Broadening process. They aim to share learnings and progress from the eight Broadening city-regions (BCRs) – previously referred to as extension city-regions – while offering policy recommendations and identifying potential financial streams for implementing integrated food policies. This first progress report provides an overview of FoodCLIC’s Broadening process and its first two phases (Preparation and Strategic Planning) which took place between June 2023 - May 2025 and specifically focuses on the learnings from baseline assessments and stakeholder mappings of BCRs. Based on the information gathered, the second progress report, expected to be submitted in August 2026, will be detailing visioning and action planning activities of the city-regions.

The development of Deliverables 5.9 and 5.12 is led by ICLEI World Secretariat, while ICLEI Africa Secretariat (ICLEI AS) and ICLEI European Secretariat (ICLEI ES) contribute to the reports with information gathered throughout the Broadening process, particularly from Broadening activities held with each BCR. In particular, the reports are aligned with and summarize information from the Broadening Reports (reinterpretation of the Grant Agreement’s specified “situation analysis” report) drafted throughout the process by each BCR with support of ICLEI AS and ES colleagues. The progress reports will also serve as input into D4.4 Report on the comparative analysis of the Living Labs (HUB, M51), which will be discussed during the project’s final international conference.

3. FOODCLIC BROADENING: OBJECTIVES AND PROGRESS OVERVIEW

2.1 OBJECTIVES

FoodCLIC's Broadening process is a part of the project's Phase 5 Anchoring and Broadening, aiming to ensure the continuation of the policies, actions, and initiatives upon project end, as well as the broad dissemination of key findings and successful outcomes across and beyond Europe. The Broadening process aims to facilitate the sharing, dialogue, translation and context-based adoption of good practices and lessons learned between FoodCLIC Pilot city-regions (Living Labs - LLs) and BCRs. To support a more global contextualization, in addition to five BCRs from Europe, three of the BCRs are located in Africa. Using the tools and approaches that have been co-developed with LLs, the eight BCRs are supported in their efforts to develop science, policy and society connections for food system transformation grounded in local action in city-region food environments. The BCRs will:

- Conduct baseline assessments, stakeholder mappings and draft a vision for their city-region food systems.
- Create or strengthen a multi-stakeholder group focusing on food policy, initiatives, and activities.
- Strengthen linkages with other city-regions through peer-to-peer exchanges.
- Identify pathways for change towards a city-region food strategy integrated across scale and sectors.

As outlined in the Broadening Plan, BCRs are implementing a portion of the FoodCLIC process, focusing on Steps 1 to 7 and, if identified as priority, Step 8 of the 10-Step FoodCLIC process described below. This report focuses on Steps 1 to 5, while also giving insights into the overarching preparatory work within the consortium.

FoodCLIC Phase 5 - Anchoring and Broadening

Scope of the First Progress Report

I) Preparatory Work within Consortium

Development of Broadening Plan and Scope of Work
Call for Applications and Selection of BCRs

II) Broadening Process with City-Regions Preparation

Step 1: Secure commitment
Step 2: Develop a way of working together
Step 3: Stakeholder identification and mapping
Step 4: Establish co-creation with stakeholders

Strategic Planning

Step 5: Analyse the current state of the local food system

Scope of the Second Progress Report

Strategic Planning II

Step 6: Develop a long-term vision
Step 7: Identify pathways for change
Step 8: Agree on priorities, timelines, responsibilities and resources

2.2 PROGRESS REVIEW

I) Preparatory Work within Consortium

Development of Broadening Plan and Scope of Work

FoodCLIC's Broadening work commenced officially in June 2023. ICLEI World Secretariat, European Secretariat, and Africa Secretariat (hereafter the ICLEI Broadening Team) outlined process goals, established a modus operandi, defined the scope of work and possible timelines, and set up the application process. These elements served as a basis for [D5.6 Broadening Plan on Extension City-Regions](#).

Attention was placed on ensuring flexibility and groundedness of FoodCLIC's Broadening approach in co-creation, a collaborative approach to engagement allowing for actors involved to co-develop inclusive and sustainable mechanisms for change. As such, while the FoodCLIC Broadening process is to provide a structure, tools, support and templates, it is envisioned to be responsive and open to adapting to the requests and needs of the BCRs. 'Extension' as it was originally called in the grant agreement, has thus been relabeled as 'Broadening' to move away from the idea of a simple replication of FoodCLIC's approaches. Instead, the focus is on the flexible nature of the process and

on meeting the actual needs of the BCRs, with activities responding to their individually determined goals.

Call for Applications and Selection of BCRs

To ensure fairness and transparency of the selection process, BCRs were selected through an open call. The process of preparing the call involved the creation of a draft set of criteria for the selection of BCRs, which were additionally consulted with the Think Tank at the 2nd Think Tank meeting in Lisbon in September 2023.

Process for becoming a FoodCLIC Broadening city-region.

In November 2023, the [call for participation](#) was launched to select three African city-regions and five European city-regions to act as FoodCLIC's BCRs. The call was amplified and shared by FoodCLIC partners in their networks, reaching over 140 city-regions through direct channels. A total of 50 applications (31 from Africa, 19 from Europe) were received by March 2024 and assessed against the consulted [set of transparent criteria](#) by ICLEI's selection committee to create an initial shortlist of suitable candidates. Based on such criteria, including formal requirements and quality of responses, additional factors including geographic diversity and selecting cities at different stages of their food systems transformation (FST) journey were considered. A decision was made to also allow non-governmental entities to apply on behalf of the city-region, provided they could demonstrate close links to the municipality. This was done in the acknowledgement that FoodCLIC is a project focusing on 'city-regional' food systems with a multi-actor approach, and that sometimes, the coordinating actor may not be the city itself, i.e. in the case of a Food Policy Council or community development context where a trusted NGO might work in closer partnership with the municipality. This also acknowledges the science-policy-practice interface, in which a research organization or practice partner may be a great connector to the policy sphere. As such, and in consultation with project coordination, partners and the Think Tank, the following applicants and city-regions were finally chosen:

Selected BCRs and Applicants

Municipality

Ebolowa, Cameroon: Ebolowa City Council

EThekweni, South Africa: eThekweni Municipality

Tirana, Albania: Municipality of Tirana

Wrocław, Poland: Wrocław Municipality

Thessaloniki, Greece: City of Thessaloniki- Resilient officer

Research Institution

Fort Portal, Uganda: Kabarole Research and Resource Center

Environmental NGO

Tbilisi, Georgia: Greens Movement of Georgia and Friends of the Earth - Georgia in collaboration with the Tbilisi City Hall

Food Policy Council

Freiburg, Germany: Ernährungsrat Freiburg & Region e.V.

The countries marked in green represent the eight city-regional FoodCLIC living labs: Aarhus, Amsterdam, Barcelona, Berlin, Budapest Brasov, Lisbon and Lucca.

II) Broadening Process with City-Regions

PREPARATION

Onboarding and First Peer-To-Peer Exchange

Applicants were given until May to confirm their participation and **secure commitment (Step 1)**. Upon acceptance, ICLEI AS and ES engaged with selected BCRs within their respective regions to define the best way of working together and outline the scope of activities, roles, and responsibilities in detail. As a result, approaches taken by African BCRs and European BCRs differed in a few ways.

To strengthen the collaboration between the African BCRs and ICLEI Africa, steering committees were established in each of the cities to coordinate FoodCLIC activities with members from local government, local organizations ICLEI Africa. The steering committees in each city convened through online **bi-weekly check-ins, planning and coordination meetings**. The intention of these meetings was to develop a shared strategy for each BCR, identify key gaps for mapping and baseline assessment and to share FoodCLIC tools as part designing and setting the agenda of the workshop. All members of the committee were given the opportunity to add to the agenda and meetings were convened in an open and participatory manner to ensure FoodCLIC activities support each of the city-regions' needs and intentions. Establishing these committees offered several benefits of fostering a sense of ownership, accountability, and buy-in, **enabling genuine co-creation and continuity throughout the process** and ensuring that the voices of the BCRs were central in the workshop design. These steering committees also helped with the delegation of key responsibilities, such as stakeholder mapping and managing invitations to local actors, enhancing visibility and engagement.

European BCRs adopted a different approach, with regular 1-on-1 meetings being offered monthly and held online for up to 45 minutes, complemented by consistent email communication. These sessions offered a dedicated space for both structured updates and informal exchange and helped track progress, clarify objectives, and address questions, while also serving as reminders for upcoming actions and events. A preliminary **workplan (Step 2)** was also agreed upon.

To support and complement the broadening activities carried out within city-regions, co-organised virtual workshops and peer-to-peer exchanges serve as key cornerstones of the Broadening process, drawing on the learnings and experiences of both LLs and BCRs. An initial **virtual onboarding** took place on May 24th, 2024, welcoming the eight selected city-regions into the FoodCLIC project, introducing the process, and allowing space for BCRs to introduce their city-region contexts. This overview was also presented to the broader FoodCLIC consortium at the annual consortium meeting which took place in Berlin between October 21st and 24th, 2024. The last day of the meeting was specifically reserved for a **first peer-to-peer exchange** ([Discussion Notes, first Peer-to-Peer Exchange](#)), consisting of table talks between representatives from the LLs and BCRs with the goal

of relationship-building and sharing approaches and perspectives on: with the goal of relationship-building and sharing approaches and perspectives on:

- Challenges and opportunities for food systems work within city-regions and experiences or motivations for FoodCLIC work in general.
- Specific topics including food policy councils and multi-stakeholder groups, engagement and collaboration, food quality and nutrition, understanding and measuring impact, and food environments and supply chains.

Preparation of Broadening Activities

Kicking off the Broadening activities linked to Stakeholder Mapping and Co-Creation and Baseline Assessments, ICLEI hosted a first online webinar in November 2024 to present the suite of FoodCLIC tools, methodologies and templates used for the activities in LLs, and to enable BCRs to exchange on the pending local workshops. The contents of the preparatory webinar were extracted from LL activity reports, [D1.5 Updated guidelines for the BCRs](#) and the [Baseline Assessments and Stakeholder Mapping Guidance & Inspiration](#) document, co-created by Vrije Universiteit and ICS-ULisboa and adapted by ICLEI.

Prior to the workshops, the BCRs were asked to list the mapping and assessment activities that have already taken place within the city-region and present a condensed version of their processes within the webinar. Following a presentation of tools to map food systems stakeholders, policies, initiatives and food environments, city-region representatives were placed in breakout groups to discuss concrete goals, challenges and opportunities they foresee throughout the process, and which stakeholders they consider key in engaging with further. Below is an overview of the goals the BCRs mentioned in the initial phases of the Broadening process. In the following phases of workshop planning, some of these goals have become more concrete or have been adapted to serve a specific purpose, as will be detailed in the dedicated sections. A summary of the information gathered during the webinar and in 1-on-1 exchanges can be found in Annex 1.

Table 1: Initial Broadening Process Goals of BCRs

City-Region	FoodCLIC Process Goals
Ebolowa	<p>Building blocks for developing a coherent food systems approach (sustainable food policy for the next decade) through policy integration, horizontal integration across municipal departments, and connecting of stakeholders across the quadruple helix</p> <p>Mapping and defining power dynamics of stakeholders</p> <p>Raising awareness on the value and importance of food systems</p> <p>#StakeholderEngagement #ActionPlan</p>

eThekwini	<p>Building blocks for the design, facilitation and creation of a Multi-Stakeholder Platform/Reference Group/Food Policy Council</p> <p>Supporting the development of eThekwini Food Strategy</p> <p>#FoodPolicyCouncil #FoodStrategy #FoodSecurity #Affordability #Nutrition #HorizontalIntegration</p>
Fort Portal	<p>Working on food safety, with potential to feed into the draft food safety ordinance</p> <p>#StakeholderEngagement #FoodSafety</p>
Freiburg	<p>Establishment of the House of Food (food hub)</p> <p>#FoodHub #StakeholderEngagement #SustainabilityClimateChange</p>
Tbilisi	<p>Laying the groundwork for the creation of a Food Council to help direct the discussion and bringing actors together</p> <p>#Inclusion #Connectivities</p>
Thessaloniki	<p>Integrating the food policy into the climate neutrality strategy and the city climate contract</p> <p>Strengthening and widening FPC along the Quadruple Helix</p> <p>Deepening the participative work, moving from policy guidelines to action planning</p> <p>#StakeholderCollaboration #FoodPolicy #ClimateChangeBiodiversity #ActionPlanning</p>
Tirana	<p>Continuing to engage with stakeholders and laying the foundation for the establishment of the policy council, ensuring its integration within the broader political context</p> <p>#FoodPolicyCouncil #StakeholderEngagement #FoodPolicy #Markets</p>
Wrocław	<p>Strengthening stakeholder engagement with a focus on food security and crisis management</p> <p>Engaging food-deprived groups</p> <p>#FoodSystemsResilience #StakeholderEngagement</p>

To offer BCRs additional opportunities for peer-to-peer learning grounded in real-life experiences of urban policy transformation, synergies with the Horizon Project CLEVERFOOD were also encouraged. In the scope of CLEVERFOOD, supported directly by the work in FoodCLIC LLs, public engagement tools for stakeholder mappings were developed, and BCRs were encouraged to attend a webinar in March 2025 shortly before the local workshops, and benefit from the FoodCLIC Amsterdam LL giving an overview of their work mobilizing stakeholders and assessing their food system. Additional webinars on creating an outreach plan and visioning and strategic planning are also slated to take place in the later half of 2025.

First Broadening Workshops on Stakeholder Mapping, Co-Creation and Baseline Assessments in BCRs

The eight BCRs conducted their first local workshops between March and May 2025. Across the board, BCRs chose to dedicate large portions of their workshops on **stakeholder mapping and co-creation (Step 3 and Step 4)**, supported by work on **baseline assessments (Step 5)** to varying extents. African BCRs, for example, were able to do more baseline assessments as the workshops were conducted over 2-3 days, creating a breadth and depth of knowledge benefiting from insights and discussions of site visits and participatory mapping exercises. The variation in focus among BCRs can also be attributed more generally to different resources and institutional contexts within which they operate. Comprehensive mapping of policies and initiatives often requires time, analytical support and access to data, resources that are more easily mobilized when cities collaborate with research partners. In the absence of such support, many city-regions chose to prioritize stakeholder mapping as a practical and more accessible starting point for understanding their local food systems. At the same time, some city-regions, such as Wrocław, were able to build on previous efforts, i.e. the presence of a dedicated food policy coordinator and prior assessments that were available. This allowed them to build upon existing knowledge and engage in more advanced baseline analysis, highlighting how internal capacities and pre-existing institutional knowledge can significantly shape the scope and depth of early food systems work within city-regions.

An overview of the main purpose of the first workshop is provided in the following table. A detailed summary of key activities, results and learnings per Broadening city-region are provided in the following section (Section 3: **Summary of Broadening Work per City**) based on excerpts from the Broadening Reports written by the BCR representatives and insights from the ICLEI Broadening Team. The complete reports as of 18 June 2025 per BCRs can be found [here](#).

Table 2: First Workshop on Stakeholder Mapping and Baseline Assessments at a Glance

City-Regions	Focus of Stakeholder Mapping and Baseline Assessment Workshop	Activities	Main CLIC Focus
Ebolowa	Mapping stakeholders, interdependencies and opportunities to promote local production and self-sufficiency in Ebolowa's food system	Stakeholder Mapping, Inclusivity Scan, Policy and Activity Mapping, Assessment of Opportunities for Production, Exploring Food Environments and Site Visits	#Connectivities #Linkages
eThekwini	Uncovering lessons, building relationships, and catalyzing momentum for the development of eThekwini's food strategy	Stakeholder Mapping, Inclusivity Scan, Exploring Food Environments and Site	#Connectivities #Inclusion

		Visits, Whatsapp Voice Mapping	
Fort Portal	Deepening commitments to inclusive food governance by co-creating a city-wide food safety strategy grounded in lived experiences, multi-sectoral collaboration, and systems thinking	Stakeholder Mapping, Photo and Voice Mapping, Site Visits, SWOT Analysis	#Inclusion #Co-Benefits #Connectivities
Freiburg	Participatory consolidation, update and re-organization of previous stakeholder mapping relevant for the development of the food hub 'HOF Centre for Food and Agriculture'	Consolidation of Stakeholder Mapping	#Co-benefits #Linkages
Tbilisi	Sharing experiences, assessing gaps in food governance, and co-producing a snapshot of Tbilisi's food policy landscape	Stakeholder Mapping using Quadruple Helix, Power vs. Interest Matrix, Power Tree Analysis	#Co-benefits #Inclusion
Thessaloniki	Discussing sustainable nutrition and urban metabolism in the effort to achieve climate neutrality	Presentations, Stakeholder Mapping, Inclusivity Template	#Co-Benefits #Connectivities
Tirana	Shaping Tirana's transition towards a healthier, safer, and more sustainable food system - Challenges and Opportunities	Presentations, Stakeholder Mapping, Inclusivity Template	#Co-Benefits #Inclusions #Connectivities
Wrocław	Analyzing strengths and weaknesses of the Wrocław Functional Area to promote food security and crisis resilience in the region	SWOT Analysis, Stakeholder Mapping	#Linkages #Connectivities #Inclusion

4. SUMMARY OF BROADENING WORK PER CITY-REGION

The summaries below draw on insights and findings from the FoodCLIC Broadening Reports developed by participating city-regions. We gratefully acknowledge the work and contributions of each local team and workshop participants, whose reflections and documentation have informed the content and analysis presented here.

3.1 EBOLOWA

Ebolowa, the administrative center of Cameroon's Southern Region, is a key crossroads city and an important agricultural hub, renowned for its production of cocoa, plantains, cassava, and vegetables.

Challenges

Ebolowa's food environment faces significant environmental, economic and social vulnerabilities that undermine both food security and food system transformation efforts. Poor hygiene standards at slaughterhouses and markets, as well as the limited waste collection capacities contribute to rising public health risks. Underdeveloped distribution and processing infrastructures also constrain the competitiveness of local food products, and many small-scale farmers and informal vendors remain excluded from formal value chains, limiting their access to financial and technical support schemes.

Existing Transformation Efforts

With a young and dynamic population, Ebolowa plays a leading role in regional development and is recognized as the third African Fairtrade town, reinforcing its commitment to sustainable and ethical trade practices. Ongoing initiatives to structure agricultural sectors and support producers, notably through CAPEF and MINADER and MINEPIA programmes, are helping to strengthen local technical and financial capacities. Local initiatives support micro fish farming and livestock projects, while reforestation efforts enhance both environmental sustainability and food security, with the city encouraging young people and students to engage in agro-entrepreneurship, ensuring the next generation is involved in food production.

Nevertheless, local authorities (the Regional Council, CUE and district councils) and private actors are critical to infrastructure and distribution development but are constrained by budgetary and logistical limitations. Local producers and processors demonstrate strong potential for innovation and agro-ecological adaptation, but their limited access to modern equipment, competitive markets and financing hampers their ability to drive effective food system transformation. An integrated approach - combining capacity building, improved governance and resource mobilization - is essential to maximize stakeholder impact.

FoodCLIC Broadening Goal

A key priority for Ebolowa is the establishment of a sustainable food policy to guide the city's development over the next decade, as part of a broader effort to equip Ebolowa to implement effective, collaborative, multi-sectoral food policies in light of the above-mentioned challenges.

Broadening Workshop #1

The FoodCLIC workshop, held for three days between February 25th and 27th, 2025 at the Hotel Florence marked the official launch of the project in Ebolowa. It provided an opportunity for structured dialogue between food system stakeholders and focused on three main areas:

- *Stakeholder mapping and assessment*: identification of key players, analysis of existing collaborations and gaps to be filled.
- *Capacity-building and learning exchange*: an introduction to systemic approaches to food governance and the sharing of local initiatives.
- *Exploring the potential of a Food Policy Council* that would bring together public, private and non-government sector stakeholders together.

Adapted from and guided by the FoodCLIC Broadening Guidance and Inspirations document, a series of activities were undertaken as part of strengthening the understanding and coordination around Ebolowa's food system. **Stakeholder mapping** activities included a capacity-building session with a presentation focusing on existing food-related work across various municipal departments and stakeholders, in addition to a participatory exercise identifying key missing actors and an analysis of power dynamics and potential areas for collaboration. Alongside these efforts, **baseline**

assessments included initiative mappings and an exploration and discussion of Ebolowa's relevant **food environments**. This included a review of policies and activities in the Commune Urbaine d'Ebolowa, and field site visits to the municipal abattoir, market, MIRAP shop, municipal landfill site and greenhouses to the greenhouses of the Collège Régional d'Agriculture (CRA).

Workshop Outcomes

The first workshop was a momentous occasion, as it was the first time that different city departments and actors came together to discuss broader issues around food systems in the city-region. Three main lessons were learned from the FoodCLIC Broadening workshop. First, the

workshop highlighted the deep interconnectedness among food system stakeholders. It played a key role in further strengthening this interconnectedness and in identifying stakeholders that are not included in the current network of actors while fostering a shared understanding among participants of the complex interdependencies within the system. It became clear that each actor - whether involved in production, processing, distribution, or governance - has a direct or indirect impact on the rest of the system. Secondly, the workshop also revealed significant vulnerabilities, particularly

related to inadequate infrastructure and unsanitary conditions in key areas such as markets, abattoirs, and urban public spaces. These challenges pose a risk to food safety and public health, underlining the urgency of targeted interventions to ensure access to healthy food regardless of its origin. Finally, the workshop highlighted the importance of involving local academic and sectoral experts, especially from universities and specialized institutions, in order to offer valuable resources needed to inform context-appropriate solutions.

	Gaps Identified	Key Learnings and Recommendations from Participants
Co-benefits	Unsanitary slaughter facilities and markets	Stakeholders and policy mapping confirmed the city's heavy dependence on food imports, with local production falling short of covering the needs of the city. Field visits highlighted critical infrastructure issues, especially at the municipal abattoir, markets and in waste management.
	Sub-optimal waste management	The region's fertile land offers strong potential for the adoption of productive, climate-smart agroecological practices
Linkages	Low agro-pastoral production	Local authorities (the Regional Council, CUE and district councils) and private actors are critical to infrastructure and distribution development, but are constrained by budgetary and logistical limitations.
	Dependence on products from outside the region	Local producers and processors demonstrate strong potential for innovation and agro-ecological adaptation, but their limited access to modern equipment, competitive markets and financing hampers their ability to drive effective food system transformation. An integrated approach—combining capacity building, improved governance and resource mobilization—is essential to maximize stakeholder impact.
	Poorly organized markets	
Inclusion	Underrepresentation of small-scale farmers, informal vendors and vulnerable groups	<p>Inclusivity remains a challenge in Ebolowa, with vulnerable groups, especially women and youth, still struggling to access available support and funding mechanisms.</p> <p>One finding of the workshop in particular was the underrepresentation of small-scale farmers and informal vendors, who, although essential links in the system, have limited influence over political and strategic decisions. The lack of representation from the Ministry of the Environment, banking institutions, restaurateurs, transporters and end-consumers also demonstrated the need for more cross-sector coordination. This lesson is particularly relevant to the food systems strategy, as it confirms that each link in the food chain is interdependent and that the involvement of all stakeholders is essential for effective and coherent action. This realization highlights the urgent need for a structured framework for multi-stakeholder dialogue, bringing together all sectors - from land management to processing and distribution - to co-develop a food policy rooted in local realities.</p>
Connectivities	Inadequate funding and weak collaboration between stakeholders	The stakeholder assessment revealed varying strengths across stakeholder categories, and the workshop served as a valuable reminder of their capacities. Ministries such as MINADER and MINEPIA have strong regulatory frameworks and the mandate to guide agricultural policies, yet their impact is limited by inadequate funding and weak inter-sectoral coordination. Professional organizations and cooperatives, including CAPEF and agricultural unions, play a key role in supporting producers and providing access to finance, but face structural and representational challenges—particularly in advocating for small producers.

Reflection on Broadening Process and Tools

A number of FoodCLIC tools were used, such as the system elements diagram, the quadruple helix matrix, the preliminary presentation and the power map table. Some of them were held in plenary sessions while others in group settings, such as the Inclusivity mapping template on who is missing and the inventory of policies. This last tool in particular proved more challenging for participants to engage with. To address this, stickers were used as a more accessible alternative, helping participants identify relevant initiatives and their roles within the food system. Participatory mapping via field visits was seen as essential for mapping the reality and nature of the city's infrastructure. It gave a new, dynamic direction to discussions, which were based on real, measured facts.

Next Steps

Establishing a Food Policy Council emerged as a strategic priority to improve governance, enhance planning and move toward a more self-sufficient food system in Ebolowa. The participants also discussed the need for a study of a pilot district or sector of the city to collect the data required for planning the Ebolowa system at a future workshop.

3.2 ETHEKWINI

The eThekweni Metropolitan Municipality, which includes the city of Durban and surrounding rural and peri-urban areas, is located on the east coast of South Africa in KwaZulu-Natal. It is home to approximately 4 million people across 110 wards - 68% of which are suburban or rural and historically underdeveloped. eThekweni's food system can be characterized by a mixed food economy including formal food businesses and supermarkets alongside a vibrant informal economy made up of diverse small businesses, including traders, markets, agribusinesses, and subsistence producers, strong agroecological diversity in the region, allowing a variety of foods to be produced locally and a history of civil society engagement and research expertise in food systems.

Challenges

Roughly 40% of residents live in poverty, and many continue to experience food and nutrition insecurity, particularly in informal settlements. While technically food secure at times, the city lacks resilience, as evidenced during the COVID-19 pandemic, when food supply disruptions significantly impacted low-income households. Further compounding the issue are fragmented governance structures, the absence of a guiding food policy or strategy, and environmental risks such as droughts and floods, which disrupt food production and access.

Existing Food Systems Transformation Efforts

eThekweni Municipality has implemented a range of initiatives to strengthen its local food system, focusing on sustainability, equity, and resilience. Key municipal actions include the One Home, One Garden programme, which has supported over 1,100 households in establishing home gardens, the development of seven agri-hubs and a farmer support programme benefiting over 800 small-scale farmers, and the operation of 87 soup kitchens serving 59,000 people daily. The city also supports more than 500 community and school gardens and has developed an Agribusiness Master Plan to guide inclusive agricultural development. Collaborations have been central to these efforts: with the Southern Africa Food Lab (SAFL), the Woza Nami pilot project at Inchanga agri-hub supported 35 agroecological farmers (80% women), and a tailor-made training programme helped strengthen interdepartmental collaboration and participatory planning. Through the SHEFS research project, eThekweni also explored the role of trees and green spaces in improving food security, finding strong potential to integrate natural assets into food system strategies. Together, these efforts demonstrate a growing commitment to inclusive, locally rooted food systems transformation.

FoodCLIC Broadening Goal

eThekweni has long expressed a commitment to developing a food security strategy. However, for nearly four years, this process remained dormant due to limited municipal capacity and resources. In 2024, this effort was revived with support from the FoodCLIC project: working towards the development of a locally grounded and collectively owned food strategy. As part of this process, eThekweni used participatory tools to map food environments, identify gaps, strengths and priorities, map out food initiatives and existing programmes and integrate into relevant policies, and build cross-departmental collaboration within the municipality.

Broadening Workshop #1

eThekweni’s three-day Mapping and Baseline Assessment Workshop, held from March 11th-13th, 2025, convened with four core aims to 1) explore the lived experiences of residents in relation to the local food system; 2) assess existing food governance structures and dynamics; 3) mapping mandates, policies, departments, and stakeholder relationships; 4) co-develop a framework for next steps. Adapted from and guided by the FoodCLIC Broadening Guidance and Inspirations document, activities undertaken include the following **Stakeholder Mapping** adapted to be divided by sector (Waste, Production/Agriculture, Processing & Agribusiness, Markets & Distribution, Governance & Implementation, Consumption & Nutrition) in addition to identifying missing actors that are important to include in each category. Additionally, participants took time to develop and brainstorm sector specific recommendations for developing more inclusive sustainable and resilient food systems. Lastly, workshops also explored eThekweni’s **food environments** and lived experiences via field visits, such as to the town’s Fresh Produce Market, and adapted Whatsapp Voice Mapping activity.

Workshop Outcomes

Ultimately, the stakeholder mapping and baseline assessment process offered both a snapshot of the current food system landscape in eThekweni and a strategic springboard for future planning. It helped surface lessons, build relationships, and catalyze momentum toward a more resilient, inclusive, and sustainable urban food system. The workshop also highlighted the importance of designing the process around energy, responsiveness, and real-time relevance. We learned that strategic framing significantly influences participation - framing the food strategy as an agricultural initiative limited broader involvement. It is critical to clearly communicate the multi-sectoral, systemic nature of food systems work.

	Gaps Identified	Key Learnings and Recommendations from Participants
Co-benefits	<p>Misperception that food systems strategy is only about agriculture</p> <p>Underrepresentation of key municipal departments</p> <p>Limited integration of disaster risk into food planning</p>	<p>The framing of the workshop under the Agroecology Unit may have unintentionally limited broader participation. However, participants made it clear that the most pressing issues they face relate to health, governance, and economic development, not agriculture alone. This highlighted a need to shift strategic messaging toward inclusive, holistic food systems transformation. The food system also remains vulnerable to environmental risks. Fieldwork in Umlazi, Durban’s largest township, underscored how floods exacerbate food insecurity and revealed the need to integrate disaster risk planning into food policy frameworks. To address these, one of the key outcomes of the workshop was a recommendation to establish a formalized multi-departmental and multi-stakeholder task team to coordinate, guide, and oversee the strategy’s development and implementation.</p>
Linkages	<p>Insufficient support for small-scale producers and informal actors</p>	<p>Smallholder farmers, informal traders, and processors continue to face challenges in accessing markets, complying with regulations, and securing infrastructure. The Durban Fresh Produce Market, while economically significant, lacks mechanisms to support small-scale, organic, or informal producers, and reinvestment into market infrastructure is limited.</p>
Inclusion	<p>Limited participation of private sector, informal traders, traditional leaders</p>	<p>A major attempt of the workshop was to include vulnerable actors in the process. The workshop successfully managed to include smallholder and subsistence farmers from peri-urban and historically marginalized areas, civil society organizations working with low-income households, academics generating data on food insecurity and nutrition, and NGOs with</p>

	<p>Weak link between food strategy and lived realities</p>	<p>a focus on environmental and health equity. These actors brought vital insights into how the current food system affects communities facing poverty, food insecurity, exclusion from policy processes, and climate-related vulnerability.</p> <p>The participatory “Our Food Stories” session, field visits, and reflections reinforced the importance of rooting the strategy in people’s lived experiences. Issues like urban food insecurity, market access, and the erosion of indigenous food cultures emerged as priority concerns. Building on local programmes such as the UKZN Sustainable and Healthy Food Systems Programme, Groundwork’s Zero Waste Initiative, and the Climate Change Implementation Plan will ensure the strategy reflects both community realities and municipal priorities.</p>
<p>Connectivities</p>	<p>Siloed governance and unclear mandates</p> <p>Absence of alignment with existing municipal plans</p>	<p>A central learning was the absence of key departments such as Social Development, Education, Economic Development, and Risk Management. Despite extensive invitations sent by the Agroecology Unit, many departments did not attend—potentially due to the perception that this was an agriculture-specific process. This underrepresentation affected cross-sectoral dialogue and limited opportunities for alignment with broader municipal strategies.</p>

Reflection on Broadening Process and Tools

Several tools from the FoodCLIC Guidance and Inspiration document were used, including templates for stakeholder mapping and Inclusivity template on which actors are missing. These were helpful in structuring conversations and surfacing missing actors. The photovoice method was also adapted into a WhatsApp-based format, which allowed participants to share reflections informally and extended the participatory ethos of the workshop beyond formal sessions.

Next Steps

Additional mapping is needed to fully understand the institutional and policy landscape shaping the food system. ICLEI Africa will lead the next phase of work, focusing specifically on mapping local government departments relevant to food, as well as multi-level policy connections. This next phase will strengthen the foundation for interdepartmental coordination and support the development of a more inclusive and grounded food strategy.

3.3 FORT PORTAL

Fort Portal, situated in the Kabarole District of western Uganda, is marked by a paradox of abundant food production and high levels of food insecurity and malnutrition. Its food system is shaped by smallholder farmers, vendors, processors, and community groups, operating across both formal and informal sectors.

Challenges

Fort Portal faces entrenched challenges in food safety and urban health, including unsafe food handling, poor sanitation, contaminated environments, inadequate market infrastructure, and limited cold storage. Waste management remains a critical issue, marked by open burning, food loss, and impacts on air quality and public health. Fragmented coordination, limited technical capacity, and the exclusion of vulnerable voices further hinder systemic progress.

Existing Food Systems Transformation Efforts

A key driving force behind Fort Portal's food systems transformation has been the partnership between Fort Portal City Council and the Kabarole Research and Resource Centre (KRC), particularly through the Food Change Lab, a multi-year initiative that mobilized community voices, piloted grassroots solutions, and introduced systems thinking into local food governance. Innovative local practices, such as agroecological farming practices, post-harvest handling improvements, circular economy initiatives, and community-driven networks like the Coalition of the Willing and Orugali, demonstrate the city's readiness to experiment with sustainable solutions.

FoodCLIC Broadening Goal

Fort Portal joined FoodCLIC to build on the foundations laid by the Food Change Lab and to institutionalize its outcomes. The goal is to develop a city-level food strategy aligned with the newly gazetted food safety ordinance and national goals. Through FoodCLIC, Fort Portal is strengthening stakeholder collaboration, mapping existing initiatives and food environments, and promoting behavior change through community-based advocacy, public education, and capacity-building initiatives.

Broadening Workshop #1

Between late 2024 and mid-2025, Fort Portal implemented the first stages of the FoodCLIC process, through stakeholder mapping, capacity building, and a three-day participatory workshop in March 2025. Over the three-day workshop, diverse stakeholders of Fort Portal's food system participated to co-develop a city food safety strategy and launch the next phase of the Food Change Lab. Adapted from and guided by the FoodCLIC Broadening Guidance and Inspirations document, activities undertaken during the workshop were:

Activity 1 (Food System Capacity Building and Stakeholder Mapping):

Stakeholder engagement began with preparatory meetings between ICLEI Africa, KRC, and municipal officials to align objectives and co-develop a workshop roadmap. This was built on the already established trust and structured collaboration coming from the Food Change Lab (benefiting from existing networks such as the Coalition of the Willing and Orugali). The workshop convened diverse stakeholders, i.e. local government representatives from different

departments; researchers; market vendors; food processors; youth innovators; waste reusers; civil society organizations; and faith and cultural leaders.

Activity 2 (Who is missing and why?): Through the participatory mapping exercise, missing stakeholders were identified as well as proposed strategies for involvement. The workshop also highlighted vulnerable groups such as women smallholders, unemployed youth, informal vendors, and families lacking sanitation or refrigeration, drawing attention to the intersections between vulnerability, informality, and food safety risks. To ensure that these diverse voices were meaningfully engaged, tools such as Photo and Voice Mapping were included to allow stakeholders to share real-life experiences, grounding discussions in lived realities. Site visits uncovered issues like unsafe drying of vegetables, informal slaughtering, and polythene bag usage. Reflections linked these observations to the need for systemic reform and coordinated responses.

Activity 3 (Initiative Mapping): Participants mapped ongoing and desired initiatives, identified collaboration opportunities, and prioritized interventions using two colour-coded stickers to distinguish between current (yellow) and desired (orange) initiatives.

Activity 4 (SWOT analysis): The closing session identified internal strengths and weaknesses, as well as external opportunities and threats impacting Fort Portal's food system. This exercise provided critical insights to guide future planning and implementation of the city's emerging food safety strategy.

Workshop Outcomes

The workshop underscored that food safety is a complex systems issue that spans health, agriculture, waste management, and urban planning. Tackling it effectively requires moving beyond siloed interventions to coordinated, cross-sectoral action. Live experiences, local voices and coordination must be at the heart of policy-making because only through meaningful inclusion, solutions can truly reflect the realities on the ground and deliver lasting impact. Yet, fragmented governance remains a barrier. Bridging these gaps will require sustained collaboration, shared accountability, and a commitment to systems thinking. Participants also emphasized the urgent need for practical tools, political commitment, and continuous learning, all essential for empowering local actors and turning ambition into implementation.

	Gaps Identified	Key Learnings and Recommendations from Participants
Co-benefits	<p>Persistent food safety risks (ex. some practices, such as home-based slaughtering)</p> <p>Lack of training and infrastructure to align with safe food standards for</p>	<p>Participants emphasized the need to enforce food safety standards by combining it with public education and the establishment of regular monitoring systems. Social protection measures and incentives were also highlighted as essential to support safe food handling practices, particularly among low-income actors.</p> <p>Trained individuals and practitioners in food and nutrition can offer scalable, community-based approaches (e.g. care</p>

	<p>informal markets</p> <p>Low literacy levels and limited access to information.</p>	<p>groups model) that facilitate peer learning and outreach, presenting replicable models for wider impact. The increasing awareness of food safety risks provides fertile ground for targeted behavior change, communication, and education campaigns.</p> <p>To maximize outreach, tailored communication tools that use visual and audio formats, local languages, and culturally appropriate methods should be developed.</p>
Linkages	<p>Lack of broader recognition and support from formal governance structures for already developed innovative food production and safety practices (e.g., agroecology and aquaponics)</p> <p>Limited infrastructure (sanitation, cold storage, waste management)</p> <p>Urbanization pressures and land use constraints</p>	<p>The growing interest in urban and peri-urban agroecology can be leveraged to promote safe, climate-resilient production systems.</p> <p>Investment in basic food infrastructure and service delivery improvements are required.</p> <p>Strategic land use planning can support urban agriculture and food markets.</p>
Inclusion	<p>Limited participation of vulnerable groups and some key stakeholder categories (informal traders, waste handlers, engineers, transporters, rural producers, and NARO members)</p>	<p>Practical strategies were proposed to improve inclusivity in future planning processes, such as targeted outreach, inclusive terms of reference or consultation methods, tailored training, designing communications in local languages and accessible formats, and establishing quotas or dedicated spaces for underrepresented groups.</p>
Connectivities	<p>Significant capacity weaknesses within inspection and enforcement bodies (such as in regulatory enforcement by the Uganda National Bureau of Standards)</p> <p>Fragmented implementation and coordination across departments and between stakeholders</p>	<p>Models such as Orugali and care groups can be used as scalable approaches to improve food safety and nutrition knowledge, but also for facilitating collaboration across municipal departments.</p> <p>The introduction of the food safety ordinance creates an ideal entry point for systemic reform and stakeholder alignment.</p>

Reflection on Broadening Process and Tools

FoodCLIC tools such as Photo and Voice Mapping, stakeholder analysis, and initiative mapping were central to the workshop's success. They proved essential in capturing the invisible realities of informal food systems, enabled inclusive participation through audio-visual storytelling, and revealed spatial and actor-level gaps.

Next Steps

The workshop fostered a shared understanding of food safety as a cross-cutting issue connected to health, environment, waste, and economic activity. It affirmed that Fort Portal has both the capacity and commitment to lead in transforming urban food safety. Participants showed a strong appetite for continued collaboration and recognized that food system transformation requires not only technical solutions, but also inclusive, citizen-driven governance. The insights gathered will feed into the development of a city-level food strategy aligned with the newly gazetted food safety ordinance and national goals.

3.4 FREIBURG IM BREISGAU

Freiburg in Breisgau is a city located in the South-West of Germany, close to the French and Swiss borders. Located in the Black Forest region of Baden-Württemberg, it is part of the tri-national Upper Rhine Valley and is home to around 236,000 people. Renowned as a Green City, Freiburg is deeply committed to sustainability from multiple perspectives and is ambitiously working towards achieving carbon neutrality by 2038.

Challenges

Existing assessments revealed that only about 20% of the caloric intake from the key food groups consumed in Freiburg can currently be covered by projects from within the Regierungsbezirk Freiburg, pointing towards limited self-sufficiency of Freiburg's Food System. While the region played a historically important role in organic agriculture, with some of Germany's earliest organic farms established in the 1950s, today, 12.5% of the region's agricultural land is organically farmed - significantly above the national average but still well below the 30–40% target set by the state of Baden-Württemberg for 2030.

In terms of challenges in fostering food entrepreneurship and social cohesion at the community-level, Freiburg lacks accessible and functional co-working kitchens, storage facilities for food start-ups, and training kitchens. The small number of existing shared-use facilities is either prohibitively expensive or not designed for start-ups or small-scale operators.

Existing Food System Transformation Efforts

Since 2018, the City of Freiburg, as part of the **Baden-Württemberg Organic Region model (Die Bio-Musterregionen in Baden-Württemberg)** is strongly committed to improving its food system by strengthening organic farming along regional value chains. From a policy perspective, the City Council developed a **preliminary food strategy** for Freiburg and the surrounding region in 2022, named "**Gutes Essen für alle**" (good food for everyone). This strategy strives to improve the basic structures for an increased supply of regional and organic food, aiming to make the food system sustainable and fair for both people and the planet. Since 2018, Freiburg has also an established **Food Policy Council (Ernährungsrat)**, a multi-stakeholder network where relevant actors from agriculture, the food industry, administration, politics, civil society, and academia come together to promote regional and sustainable food. Under this initiative, the City of Freiburg has committed to several food-related topics, ranging from improving school meals composition and food education to reshaping regional supply structures and preserving the city's wholesale market. Over the years, the Food Policy Council has obtained a successful engagement of stakeholders, including politicians, private stakeholders, academics, and local practitioners. However, one challenge remains - bringing the topic of food into a central municipality and decision-makers to endorse its strategy and make food a central topic in political governance.

FoodCLIC Broadening Goal

Through the FoodCLIC project, the Freiburg Food Policy Council aims to strengthen the connection between the city and its region from a policy perspective, engage more institutional stakeholders and decision-makers to foster their commitment to the city's food policy, and support food-deprived and vulnerable groups to guarantee that everyone has fair access to food, for example, by fostering educational programs and sustainable food supply in elderly and retirement homes. Specifically, the

Food Policy Council will work on two flagship projects identified in the Climate Protection Concept and the Tourism Strategy of the city:

- a. Establishment of “House of Food (HoF)” (HOF für Ernährung und AgriKultur) - a public space to ensure accessibility to good food for everyone, through networking, educational training, and enjoyment activities
- b. “Food Märktle” - an initiative that aims to offer tailored gastronomic experiences for large event groups, enhance Freiburg’s culinary appeal for discerning visitors, and promote cultural identity through food.

Broadening Workshop #1

Freiburg’s first workshop was held on May 5th, 2025, at the University of Freiburg. The title of the three-hour workshop was ‘HOF für Ernährung & AgriKultur und nachhaltige Markthalle zusammen denken’ (Thinking of House of Food for Food & AgriCulture and Sustainable Market Hall Together).

The workshop was designed as a participatory exercise to identify, validate and expand, and map

key actors in the city-region food system. The session followed principles of co-creation and inclusivity, aiming to surface both well-known and overlooked actors while initiating early discussions about potential collaboration structures as well as actors relevant for the vision workshop. The workshop was co-organized by the Food Policy Council of Freiburg and Professor Stephan Lengsfeld’s seminar class of the University of Freiburg. This added an extra layer of expertise and helped ensure a broader co-creation methodology process.

Workshop Outcomes

Participants reviewed and validated the existing stakeholder mapping for the House of Food/Markthalle project by identifying missing actors, assessing their relevance to key focus areas, and categorizing them according to levels of power and interest. This stakeholder mapping played a dual role: it provided a structured understanding of relevant actors - their interests and interconnections - and facilitated a strategic process of engagement and mobilization. As a result, the workshop catalyzed early dialogue among key players, revealed representation gaps (stakeholder gapping) and helped initiate a shared sense of ownership. These outcomes lay the groundwork for a governance structure at the HOF Centre for Food and Agriculture that is representative, resilient, and action oriented.

	Gaps Identified	Key Learnings and Recommendations from Participants
Co-benefits	<p>Despite its importance, “Food Märktle” is rather low on the priority list for the implementation of the concept from the Freiburg Economic, Tourism and Trade Promotion Agency (FWTM)</p> <p>The idea of a sustainable market hall/HOF and the associated</p>	<p>Research and preparation of data that clearly shows the economic added value of a sustainable Market Hall/HOF and raise the prioritization of the “Food Märktle” at the FWTM</p> <p>Participation of various FWTM employees in the vision workshop (tourism, business development, market administration)</p>

	added value for the city must now also become more relevant at a local political level.	
Linkages	The lack of available location for the establishment of HOF in the city center represents a major hurdle to implementation	The concept for the sustainable market hall/HOF must also be made known to stakeholders who have knowledge of and access to vacant space in the inner-city area.

Stakeholder Mapping & Gapping		
Public Sector & Political Decision-Makers	Mapping Identified by the Food Policy Council	Stadt Freiburg Umweltschutzamt
		Stadt Freiburg Amt für Schule und Bildung
		Ministerium für Ernährung und ländlichen Raum Stuttgart (MLR)
		FWTM
		BM Buchheit
		Gemeinderät*innen
		Bio-Musterregion Freiburg
		Stadt Freiburg Mundenhof (Forstamt)
		Stadt Freiburg Stadtplanungsamt – Strategiekonzept Innenstadt
		Gapping Identified as relevant by the workshop attendees
	OB (Hom)	
	VAG	
	Münstermarkt	
	FWTM – Leerstand, Gutrun Reber	
Civil Society & Citizens	Mapping Identified by the Food Policy Council	Welcker e.V.
		zusammenleben e.V.
		AgriKultur e.V.
		Slow Food Freiburg
		Ernährungsrat Freiburg & Region
		Eine Welt Forum e.V.
		Foodsharing Freiburg e.V.
		Marktplatz Landkultur
		Stadinitiative Gemeinsam Freiburg e.V.
		Stadtelprojekt Katharinenstift (GenusZeit)
		Foodsharing Cafe Freiburg e.V.
		Fabrik für Handwerk, Kultur & Ökologie e.V.
		Vegan Freiburg e.V.
		Schulen/Nachmittagsbetreuung Private Schulen
		Acker e.V.
Gapping Identified as relevant by the workshop attendees	HDE	
	Bürger*innen	
	Marktschwärmer	

Table 3 - A representative snapshot of the stakeholder mapping and gapping resulting from the workshop

Reflection on Broadening Process and Tools

According to representatives from the Food Policy Council, one particularly fruitful step was the categorisation of stakeholders according to the quadruple helix model, which provided a useful framework for structuring engagement. The methods and planning guidance introduced by FoodCLIC also significantly supported the design and facilitation of the workshop itself. Furthermore, the collaboration with university students and researchers not only enriched the process but also exemplified how educational institutions can be integrated into long-term transformation strategies. One suggestion offered to the FoodCLIC tool development team is offer time allocation guidelines or adaptable agenda templates to better manage time across the different components of stakeholder engagement sessions.

Next Steps

Participants agreed to schedule the next workshop, focusing on visioning, prior to the region’s summer school break, aligning it with the university seminar presentation on July 21st, 2025. They committed to dedicating a half-day to the session. This decision reflects their sustained engagement, reinforces the progress made to date, and highlights the effective collaboration between the Food Policy Council and the university seminar group.

3.5 TBILISI

Tbilisi, the capital of Georgia, is a vibrant city located in the Southern Caucasus. With a population exceeding one million, it accounts for nearly one-third of the country's inhabitants. Renowned for its rich historical and cultural heritage, Tbilisi is also celebrated for its Georgian cuisine and wine, which has cemented its status as a culinary hotspot and a magnet for tourists from around the globe.

Challenges

Tbilisi is undergoing rapid development and faces increased competition for food resources between residents and tourists, coupled with a significant reliance on imported food. According to local partners, the necessity for Tbilisi to adopt policies and initiatives that bolster the resilience, security, and sustainability of its food systems is becoming crucial.

Existing food system transformation efforts

Fresh food markets have been a long-standing feature, and the surrounding areas have historically played a pivotal role in supplying the city with food. However, food system transformation efforts are a new topic in the city. Current urban policy efforts, in alignment with the City's Master Plan, are focusing on making neighborhoods more livable by integrating principles of mixed land use and green space development, to preserve and reintegrate historical food supply practices.

FoodCLIC Broadening Goal

Through the FoodCLIC project, the City of Tbilisi aims to engage key stakeholders to initiate a comprehensive dialogue on food policy that will lead to long-term, multi-sectoral, and multi-level stakeholder engagement. Key stakeholders include Tbilisi City Hall, central government agencies, private enterprises, academic institutions, and community and non-governmental organizations, particularly the young rural workforce and socially disadvantaged urban citizens. The areas of focus include exploring how the city can continue to provide locally grown food from the surrounding regions during this time of urbanization, and in particular looking into promoting food security initiatives, educational programs focused on healthy eating habits and food literacy and introducing specific food-related policies and comprehensive urban development strategies. As a concrete goal, actors will also consider comprehensive plans and designs to transform the sporadic farmers' market at Tbilisi Railway Station into a socially just hub by improving market infrastructure and incorporating green facilities.

Broadening Workshop #1

Tbilisi's first workshop was a half-day event taking place on April 17th, 2025 at Bazaleti Green Engineering Center. The workshop enabled a core group of stakeholders to share experiences, assess gaps in food governance, and co-produce a snapshot of the food policy landscape in Tbilisi. The event also provided a space for early-stage exploration of a transformative pilot project - the regeneration of the Tbilisi Railway Station market into a just and inclusive food hub - which, although not formally presented, became a recurring reference point during group discussions.

The workshop, organized by the Greens Movement of Georgia and Friends of the Earth – Georgia, two environmental NGOs, leading the project's implementation in Tbilisi. It was conducted in a hybrid format and a total of 17 participants attended (14 in person, 3 virtually). Pre-designed Zoom whiteboard and co-facilitation allowed virtual participants to contribute to visual materials and group

discussions, and informal consultations and, feedback loops were held before and after the event to complement the workshop.

Participants, both virtual and physical, work together to complete the Food Systems Power Tree during the workshop.

The workshop was framed around the CLIC methodology and co-creation principles, particularly aiming to identify exclusions and power asymmetries in the food system:

- Stakeholder Mapping using Quadruple Helix posters.
- Power vs. Interest Matrix for identifying power asymmetries.
- The Food Systems Power Tree template to map root causes, system dynamics, and transformative actions (this exercise was only partially completed due to time constraints).

The workshop also included a site visit where participants could observe apple cider production and off-grid energy systems, which provided tangible inspiration for how food and energy resilience can be co-developed at the local level.

Workshop Outcomes

The workshop served as a ‘first contact’ platform for many actors who had not previously collaborated, and informal partnerships emerged. Discussions showed a strong commitment to transforming the city’s food system to be sustainable, inclusive, and economically fair. A major learning emerged around bridging food and waste governance, with several stakeholders pointing to opportunities to reframe food waste as a resource for both environmental and social benefit.

	Gaps Identified	Key Learnings and Recommendations from Participants
Co-benefits	Food safety concerns, including high nitrate levels in vegetables and hormone-disrupting substances	Participants emphasized the urgency of improving food safety and food security. While large producers meet safety standards like HACCP, smallholders struggle with compliance. A simplified model tailored to small-scale producers was proposed.
	High financial burden of food waste on producers	With an estimated 55% of landfill waste being biological, participants stressed the need for systemic solutions. While existing regulations are in place, weak enforcement was highlighted as a barrier. Continued dialogue

		was encouraged, with mixed views on creating a new governance entity under City Hall.
	High food waste during traditional Georgian supras (feasts)	Participants highlighted the opportunity to reduce food waste through better menu planning and food preservation, as practiced by initiatives like Roots Radicals in Berlin. They also suggested reviving Georgian traditions of redistributing leftover food—such as sharing with relatives or donating to churches—and normalizing practices like taking leftovers home to reduce stigma and promote a more compassionate food culture. Recent regulatory changes removing tax burdens on food donations were seen as a positive step toward enabling surplus redistribution.
Inclusion	Lack of a dedicated food governance body within Tbilisi municipality	Participants recommended establishing a coordinating unit or food governance body as part of the FoodCLIC process to improve coherence and accountability in food system management.
	Regulatory imbalance between organized and unorganized markets	Concerns were raised about stricter enforcement on formal markets while informal actors operate with minimal oversight. Participants stressed the need for consistent food safety and quality standards across all market types. They also pointed out that if even regulated businesses face compliance challenges, conditions in unregulated sectors may be significantly more problematic.
Connectivity	Challenges in the HoReCa sector and pesticide use in vegetable production	Recommendations included supporting affordable, high-quality food for the hospitality sector and promoting Georgian culinary traditions, especially plant-based dishes like <i>mindvris pkhali</i> (მინდვრის ფხალი), on the international stage. Integrating global food expertise was seen as beneficial in enhancing food quality and sustainability.

Results of food systems power tree analysis

Reflection on Broadening Process and Tools

A diverse group of stakeholders from government, civil society, academia, and the private sector came together for collaborative analysis, mapping, and visioning. These participatory methods

helped visualize Tbilisi's current food system and foster inclusive governance and strategy-building. Stakeholders appreciated the participatory design of the session, the open facilitation style, and the focus on local relevance. They expressed interest in continuing collaboration and contributing to the development of a more coherent and responsive urban food system for Tbilisi.

Next Steps

The workshop's activities are the foundation for co-designing a localized food vision and establishing a Food Policy Network in future project stages. As a set of recommendations and next steps, participants expressed a strong desire to formalize a **Tbilisi Food Stakeholder Forum** or Food Policy Council to provide a structured platform for ongoing collaboration and policy development. A key priority moving forward is to **systematically incorporate the voices of food-insecure individuals and informal food workers in future workshops**, ensuring that their experiences and needs shape decision-making processes. To maintain inclusivity and encourage active participation, the **use of visual and hands-on methods**, such as Power Tree exercises and whiteboard activities, is recommended. Finally, **establishing regular communication and follow-up mechanisms** will be essential to sustain the momentum generated by the workshops and to ensure continuity in stakeholder engagement and policy action.

3.6 THESSALONIKI

Thessaloniki is the second-largest city of Greece, located along the Mediterranean Sea, with a metropolitan area population of around 1.1 million and a central municipality housing 300,000 people.

Challenges

Thessaloniki is significantly affected by climate change, experiencing desertification, overfishing, and biodiversity loss, which negatively impact agricultural production (Antonelli et al., 2022; Hellenic Republic, 2022; OECD, 2022). Furthermore, Greece consistently manifests high rates of childhood and adolescent obesity and falls below the EU average in achieving sustainable development goals related to reducing food waste and promoting sustainable food production (ibid.). While the Municipality of Thessaloniki has implemented various social food initiatives, such as social grocery stores, soup kitchens, and food aid programs, these efforts have remained fragmented. Until recently, the city lacked a cohesive food strategy and a dedicated governance structure, resulting in dispersed initiatives across multiple departments without a unified direction.

Although food is not a direct municipal mandate in Greece, Thessaloniki has actively advanced food systems transformation through structured, participatory processes and strategic initiatives. In 2020, Thessaloniki established a local Food Council, following a participatory process that started with the Food Trails Horizon 2020 project in cooperation with local stakeholders and local experts. The process began with an official decision by the Mayor (June 2019), followed by the creation of working groups formed to map partners and define priorities. This collaborative effort led to the adoption of Thessaloniki's first [food policy document](#) by the City Council in September 2023, positioning food as a strategic pillar in municipal planning under the leadership of the Resilience Office and the Department of Operational Planning. Additionally, over the past four years, Thessaloniki has witnessed the formation of a cluster of individuals working in the food sector, maintaining a close collaboration with the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, the International Hellenic University and the private sector.

Thessaloniki has also strengthened its food system transformation through international engagement, including signing the Milan Urban Food Policy Pact (2015), joining the Eurocities Food Thematic Group and UNESCO's Creative Cities Network for Gastronomy (2021) and launching the [Thessaloniki City of Gastronomy](#) website. Since 2010, the city has also promoted itself as a gastronomic destination (Chatzinakos, 2016), hosting the annual Thessaloniki Food Festival since 2011, and additionally advanced on urban agriculture via an urban vineyard to strengthen the connection between urban and rural areas.

FoodCLIC Broadening Goals

Thessaloniki views participation in the FoodCLIC project as an opportunity to further advance and elaborate on its initiatives. In particular, the city aims to:

- Strengthen governance issues, recognizing that food and sustainability are cross-cutting and cross-sectoral topics.
- Enhance its strategic planning to amplify and build upon its current accomplishments.
- Strengthen the urban and rural linkages by further developing urban cultivation.
- Engage all food-related stakeholders to develop a cohesive and collaborative cluster.

To achieve these goals, Thessaloniki plans to deepen the collaboration with the City Food Council through their thematic working groups, translate the food policy guidelines into concrete action plans, connect the sustainable food initiatives with climate neutrality.

FoodCLIC Broadening Workshop #1

Thessaloniki's first Broadening workshop, entitled "The importance of sustainable nutrition and urban metabolism in the effort to achieve climate neutrality" was held on May 14th, 2025, at the Town Hall, in collaboration with the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki. The workshop began with a presentation by Andreas Karadakis, Coordinator of the Thessaloniki's Food Council regarding the challenges the municipality is facing, followed by a presentation of the municipality's climate neutrality strategy for 2030 and a discussion on impacts and benefits of food systems in Thessaloniki toward climate neutrality. The FoodCLIC project was then presented and a very brief description of the "Mapping stakeholder groups across the Quadruple Helix" tool was given. The members of the Food Council had a discussion to collaboratively complete the template with further bodies that should be involved in the Food Council in the coming period, in order to work together on ways to quantify the goals of food policy, transform them into CO2 reduction and integrate them as mitigation measures into the overall climate neutrality strategy.

Workshop Outcomes

The workshop with the Food Council members resulted in the identification of local partners along the quadruple helix who are currently missing, which need to be invited and involved, including university laboratories and academic departments participating in the City Climate Contract (Academia), solidarity kitchens and social plates, cooperative catering enterprises (Civil Society), national and regional managing authorities of financial programs (Government), chefs and restaurants associations (private sector). The participants agreed that academics, government and private local partners are easier to invite and motivate to participate in the process of integrating food policy into the climate pact. On the contrary, the part of civil society is more difficult, due to a suspicion towards institutions and project-based actions.

	Gaps Identified	Key Learnings and Recommendations from Participants
Co-benefits	Thessaloniki aims to become a climate-neutral and smart city by 2030, reducing CO2 emissions expected within the boundaries of the Municipality of Thessaloniki by 80%. Achieving this goal will aid Thessaloniki into becoming a more sustainable, resilient and attractive city with positive benefits for public health, accessibility and the well-being of its citizens.	Thessaloniki will need to invest in a series of ambitious actions concerning the public space, processes and resources that are within its sphere of competence and go beyond existing plans and strategies and, on the other hand, mobilize collaborating bodies and businesses, so that targets in various sectors that are higher than the corresponding national ones are achieved. It is important that the food policy of the Municipality of Thessaloniki is integrated into the effort for climate neutrality in order to secure financial resources and overcome the governance problems it faces. In summary, it is critical that Thessaloniki works to address governance and capacity barriers, linking Food Policy with Climate neutrality, and increasing participation in the Food Council.
Connectivities	Thessaloniki faces particular challenges in terms of food	The Thessaloniki FPC represents an important step towards establishing an institution for collaboration and

	<p>governance, due to a lack of jurisdiction, the complexity and overlapping of mandates, and because of the breadth of municipal services are involved, without one being in charge. As a result, food policy remains project-based.</p> <p>While the FPC is trying to address this, it is not an integrated body within the municipality's organizational structure with the corresponding allocation of resources, both human and financial. As a result, the continuation of its activities depends largely on securing resources, primarily through European programs. This situation of precarious operation can lead to long periods of inactivity, damaging the trust and cooperation relationships among the FPC participants, and consequently negatively affecting its level of participation. At the same time, the dependency of the FPC's operation on supra-local funding may potentially link its strategic directions to agendas formed at a supra-local level rather than addressing local needs.</p>	<p>mediation between the Municipality and the local community for the city of Thessaloniki, opening up prospects for expanding collaboration or developing similar partnerships in other related sectors, such as circular economy, energy, and sustainable tourism. However, the impact of the lack of dedicated resources for its continued operation and strategic directions is an issue that needs further investigation.</p> <p>If the Thessaloniki FPC manages to overcome the challenge of sustainability, it can play a key role in the dissemination of sustainable agri-food practices at the local level, through coordinating information and awareness-raising actions, as well as supporting the establishment of spaces that promote urban agriculture and the direct connection between producers and consumers. It can also play a particularly supportive role in the expansion of Alternative Food Networks (AFNs) in Thessaloniki, for which networking between them and collaboration with different stakeholders within networks, such as the one formed within a FPC, is considered particularly important. In fact, strengthening AFNs is one of the key policy areas of the Thessaloniki FPC (FPC of the Municipality of Thessaloniki, 2023).</p>
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Next Steps

Thessaloniki's Food Council is motivated to further overcome barriers and mainstream the food policy into an overall city strategy, connecting it with climate neutrality. An integral component is to understand better how citizens perceive the climate neutrality concept and the relationship between

climate neutrality and the city's metabolism. In September, Thessaloniki's Food Council will work on updating the city's climate contract, presenting a crucial opportunity to integrate the food policy angle. This process will also involve participation in the Barcelona Challenge for Good Food and Climate initiative, which links urban food systems and food metabolism with climate neutrality goals. As next steps for Workshops 2 and 3, there is a need to invite partners that were identified to be missing in Thessaloniki's municipal council to work together, particularly those that have not been so involved or committed previously.

Participants of workshop 1 organized by the Thessaloniki's Food Council. Photo credit: Andreas Karadakis

3.7 TIRANA

Tirana is the capital city of Albania, serving as the heart of Albania's cultural, economic, and governmental activities. With approximately three million residents, it represents about one-third of the country's total population. Located in western Albania, it is surrounded by hills and Dajti Mountain to the east, overlooking the Adriatic Sea valley to the northwest.

Challenges

In recent years, Tirana has experienced rapid demographic growth and a surge in tourism, presenting significant challenges to the city's ability to ensure universal access to healthy food. Urban expansion, driven by increasing demand for residential and commercial development, is steadily converting agricultural land around the city. At the same time, a lack of supportive national policies for local food initiatives and limited municipal capacity to coordinate stakeholders highlight the urgent need to transform Tirana's food system infrastructure.

Existing Food Systems Transformation Efforts

Food system in Tirana is shaped not only by local efforts but also by national policies and regulations, which include the National Food Security Strategy (2023–2027), the Albanian Food-Based Dietary Guidelines and the Albanian Food Law No. 9863.

At the city level, the Municipality of Tirana is actively engaged in initiatives aimed at transforming its food system through participation in other two European-funded projects - FOODTRAILS - Horizon (2021-2024) and SURF - IPA SOUTH ADRIATIC (2024-2025). These efforts have fostered collaboration among diverse stakeholders to promote healthy food provision and reduce food waste. As part of the FoodTrails project, Tirana embarked on the initial stages of developing a comprehensive food policy. This initiative aims to consolidate existing fragmented food efforts and unite diverse actors, including local, governmental, and private entities. The city's focus is on addressing issues such as food waste, ensuring access to nutritious and high-quality food for all residents, while promoting sustainable food systems. In support of these goals, the city is establishing the Tirana Food Council and has signed a memorandum of understanding with 14 local stakeholders to strengthen support for implementing its food policy goals and creating its first food community. The community focuses on:

- Developing local products following the zero-kilometers model to meet the needs of both producers and consumers,
- Promoting safe and quality food produced in the Tirana area.

FoodCLIC Broadening Goals

Through the FoodCLIC project, Tirana plans to:

- Enhance the role of stakeholders in promoting healthy and organic food consumption,
- Demonstrate Tirana's innovative initiatives, including the Food Policy Council, the integration of food into spatial planning, and the emergence of an urban food policy,
- Increase the number of farmers' markets in the city and promote agreements among farmers to improve their average income and access,
- Continue the development of Tirana's Food Policy.

FoodCLIC Broadening Workshop #1

Tirana's first FoodCLIC workshop held on April 30th brought together key stakeholders from municipal institutions, academia, civil society, and the private sector to discuss strategic priorities and initiatives shaping Tirana's transition towards a healthier, safer, and more sustainable food system. The event included five expert presentations covering topics from infrastructure development to consumer behaviour, organic farming, public health, and circular economy approaches in food waste reduction, and marked a vital step in the FoodCLIC journey to engage local actors and develop evidence-based actions for transformative food system change in Tirana.

Workshop Outcomes

The workshop emphasized that transformation needs to include all voices to the table, particularly those historically marginalized since top-down strategies by themselves do not. The stakeholder involvement approach fostered a feeling of shared responsibility and dedication as well as enhanced the food system assessment. These connections provided the foundation for long-term transformation as the project moved forward, guaranteeing that the seeds of change kept growing and flourishing.

	Gaps Identified	Key Learnings and Recommendations from Speakers and Participants
Co-benefits	Unhealthy food consumption, with 39% of meals consumed outside the home, 35% of adults regularly consuming sugary drinks and a general increase of consumption of ultra-processed food consumption	One speaker advocated for the development of Short Food Supply Chains (SFSCs) and educational interventions to reshape consumer behavior and encourage healthier dietary patterns. SFSCs were proposed as a key strategy to reconnect consumers with producers, encourage healthier diets, and reduce dependency on processed foods. Emphasis was placed on consumer education as a tool for long-term behavior change.
Linkages	+350,000 smallholder and family farms play a significant role in promoting organic food and local sustainability, and in Albania's food system more generally. With Albania's small-scale farming structure as a backdrop, one presenter identified key challenges such as limited organic certification, food safety awareness, and rural poverty. A range of solutions were also proposed, including agritourism, CSA models, preservation of traditional seed varieties, and improved agricultural policies to strengthen Albania's organic and sustainable farming potential.	<p>Agropark Tirana is an ambitious initiative led by the Municipality of Tirana to establish Albania's largest wholesale and public market. The strategic vision of Agropark Tirana is to create a centralized and modern hub for producers, traders, and consumers. A presentation highlighted the park's role in reducing informality, supporting farmer cooperatives, and strengthening infrastructure for processing, storage, and marketing.</p> <p>Highlighted initiatives include of the Market Administration Agency include the: Establishment of Local Farmers' Markets; Implementation of marketing campaigns like "Eja në bahçe" ("Come to the Garden"); Infrastructure improvements for hygiene and food quality; Farmer training in production and marketing and B2B partnerships and collaborations with local and international stakeholders. The Tirana Food Council plays a key role in supporting SFSCs to boost freshness, reduce emissions, and build consumer trust.</p> <p>Agrotourism was also highlighted to promote local culinary culture and ecological practices while offering economic opportunities through merging agriculture with tourism.</p>

<p>Inclusion</p>	<p>Increasing risks associated with foodborne illnesses, chronic diseases, malnutrition and the vulnerability of children and elderly populations, particularly in the context of climate and lifestyle changes.</p>	<p>Programs aimed at the younger generation, such as teaching students to reduce their food waste and adopt healthier eating habits have shown positive results. These programs encourage families and communities to make larger shifts toward more sustainable food consumption by empowering children to make a difference. Early nutrition education should be integrated into school programs, and complemented by public awareness campaigns on food hygiene, labeling, and preparation, and institutional and media support to improve healthy food choices. Informed food choices are essential for building long-term resilience in both individual and community health.</p> <p>Tirana's inclusion scan revealed more discrepancies in representation. Discussions frequently excluded marginalized groups - smallholder farmers, migrant labourers, and low-income consumers - not because they lacked interest but rather because of difficulties of access, language, lack of official invitations, or just not perceiving themselves as "stakeholders." Additionally, there were power disparities, in which dominant voices, such as big agribusinesses, unintentionally eclipsed smaller farmers during discussion.</p>
<p>Connectivities</p>	<p>The regulatory and policy making bodies often collaborate in horizontal level and in few cases in vertical level.</p> <p>Additionally, there is limited collaboration between actors representing different categories of the helix. Usually, the collaboration is between two types (e.g. regulatory bodies and restaurant association, or academia and Ministry of Agriculture) but there are a few cases except for some projects that bring together all the actors. They lack common initiatives due to different interests.</p>	<p>Every stakeholder group brought particular strengths and challenges to the table. Local farmers, for example, had great understanding of production issues and strong community confidence, but many found it difficult to participate because of time limits or lack of access to decision-making areas. While their suggestions were occasionally too theoretical for quick application, NGOs and academics offered insightful analysis and innovation. Consumer organizations, on the other hand, were frequently divided and without a single voice in policy debates even while they might push demand for sustainable food.</p> <p>Although many interested parties were enthusiastic about changing the food system, they sometimes operate in isolation, losing chances for cooperation. Enhancing alliances between these entities, particularly between legislators and grassroots organizations, could help to reveal fresh ideas.</p>

Reflection on Broadening Process and Tools

Many people, especially those in the business sector (such as small producers and retailers) and civil society, didn't know what food systems thinking was or didn't see how the FoodCLIC initiative might help them right away. Tirana used a participative communication method, working with local multipliers including municipal officials, schools, and community leaders, to spread the word, in addition to storytelling to turn technical ideas into real-life problems, such as how to get food, make it affordable, and make it last. The FoodCLIC tools, namely the Quadruple Helix model and the Stakeholder mapping model, were adopted partially and the socio-economic and cultural settings of Tirana were taken into account when adapting tools to make them more relevant and effective. Tirana was able to enhance the versatility of these tools to align with various urban environments and create user-friendly interfaces, thereby enabling a wider audience to utilize them. Materials were translated into local languages, and data particular to regions were incorporated as part of this

process. Thus, while the tools are valuable for cross-city learning, one key takeaway is that they need localization. Additionally, further training, webinars and case studies could improve their ease of use and would boost uptake.

Next Steps

Due to the ever-changing nature of food systems, it remains essential to continue to assess current practices and develop new ones in order to successfully adapt to new possibilities and threats. In the future, Tirana plans to expand upon these efforts by improving data gathering methods, fortifying institutional capacities, and encouraging a spirit of creativity and inclusion in its food system. The stakeholder mapping approach particularly was a wake-up call; it revealed who was actually driving change and who was being left out. On that end, the city of Tirana plans to build more accessible venues for conversation to let politicians and underprivileged people connect, support grassroots voices by means of capacity-building, and try innovative involvement, such as participatory budgeting, to reach those currently absent. Finally, Tirana is also committed to creating a new farmers market to optimize supply chains and is actively developing its food identity to shape the future of its agrifood system.

3.8 WROCLAW

Wrocław, located in the Lower Silesia region of southwestern Poland, has a population exceeding 600,000, which has increased to over 800,000 residents as a result of a growth of immigrants and refugees from Ukraine due to the Russian war on Ukraine. Known as the city of 350 dwarfs, Wrocław stands out not only as a major urban center but also as a vibrant cultural hub.

Challenges

Currently, some of the biggest risks that the region is facing are droughts, flooding or disrupted supply chain, as fueled by the Covid-19 pandemic in 2020, the refugee crisis in 2022 related to the war in Ukraine, and a flood in 2010 and 2024. During these crises, proper coordination and distribution of food was crucial to providing support to the most vulnerable and affected groups.

Existing Food Systems Transformation Efforts

Historically, food was not a significant topic in Wrocław's strategic and policy documents. The city's engagement with food topics began with the [Fair Local Green Deals](#), a project aimed at adapting the European Green Deal at the local level through an approach involving citizens and other local stakeholders. Through this initiative, Wrocław residents initiated discussions on food, food policy, food safety, short food supply chains, and related topics, successfully engaging a broad range of stakeholders interested in developing a comprehensive and sustainable food system. The City responded by preparing an application for the Milan Urban Food Policy Pact to institutionalise the topic of food within the municipality. Since then, the city has started a municipal farm and also designated an Urban Food Policy coordinator and is currently focusing on integrating food policy into its strategic framework.

Given the interest of residents and significant pressures on Wrocław's food system due to both the climate crisis and crisis of war in Ukraine, the City of Wrocław, has decided to address the topic of food security using a regional approach rooted in working within the Wrocław Functional Area, a group of 19 municipalities in the region that cooperate for strategic purposes, with a particular emphasis on enhancing food security, towards the development of a comprehensive food policy framework. A series of maps detailing the area's characteristics, population density, crops on arable land among others have been previously created and are available within the city-regions Broadening report.

FoodCLIC Broadening Goals

Through the FoodCLIC project, the City of Wrocław aims to:

1. Work with the Wrocław Functional Area for the benefit of food security of the region, including the development of a model for food management in a crisis situation such as flooding, supply chain disruption or food contamination.
2. Further integrate food-related topics into the municipality's strategic planning to enhance food security.
3. Gain inspiration and useful insights from exchanges with other cities participating in the project. The city is committed to learning from other municipalities and adopting tools and best practices from their experiences with food policy.

FoodCLIC Broadening Workshop #1

Wrocław’s first Broadening workshop focused on “Conducting a strategic analysis on food security.” The workshop took place on April 24th, 2025, and brought together municipalities of Wrocław Functional Area and food-system related NGOs actively operating in Wrocław and the region. This was the first time this group came together and was an important step in network development. The group benefited from the wealth of information available through previous assessments prior to FoodCLIC. Therefore, this workshop was able to start building a baseline assessment specifically related to food security by focusing on the preparation of a SWOT analysis on food security of the Wrocław Functional Area and complementary mapping of stakeholders actively working in the area of food security.

Participants of workshop 1 organized by the City of Wrocław. Photo credit: Municipality of Wrocław.

Workshop Outcomes

The mapping of food security stakeholders in the Wrocław Functional Area showed participants how complex the food management system is in a crisis situation. The analysis of stakeholders and their involvement in this area is not the easiest, due to lack of commonness of this topic. There are stakeholder groups that are willing to engage in joint discussions or research, while other groups still need some time to understand the topic of food security. The baseline assessment showed that as a city and region, Wrocław is on the right track in building food security, but there are still a few elements that should be addressed, such as an analysis and accurate mapping of vulnerable groups or greater accuracy in identifying food environments.

Swot analysis - Strengths and opportunities of the Wrocław Functional Area.

	Gaps Identified	Key Learnings and Recommendations from Participants
Co-benefits	Crisis management-procedures for food distribution in a crisis situation	As a part of the FoodCLIC project, we want to develop a model for food management in the case of a crisis situation.
	Climate change and adaptation, soil depletion and drought	Increasingly intense climate change, causing increasingly prolonged droughts and heavy rains, may create favourable conditions for new animal and plant species. which may later become invasive species for crops and domestic species. The formation of new climate conditions may also favour the emergence of new insect and fungal diseases that will cause the appearance of new diseases of crops and livestock.
Linkages	Lack of adequate regulations rural-urban linkages	The Wrocław Functional Area is a group representing 19 municipalities with which the City of Wrocław cooperates most in the region in various strategic areas. Based on the prepared documents titled "Potential Food Self-sufficiency of the City of Wrocław" and "Analysis of the threats relating to the phenomenon of food terrorism in the area of the City of Wrocław" part I and part II, there is awareness that the City of Wrocław is partially dependent on these municipalities in terms of food accessibility and distribution, for the following reasons: areas of agricultural production, areas through which food transport passes or locations of logistic centers.
Inclusion	Identification of the exact location of vulnerable groups (legal restrictions)	Access to databases, including sensitive data on vulnerable people, which include flood victims, refugees, socially excluded youth, elderly people, the homeless, people at risk of poverty and representatives of other groups at risk of social exclusion. Most of these organizations are based in the City of Wrocław.
Connectivities	Lack of adequate structures at local governmental levels dealing with food policy and food security	Establish representatives or create appropriate local government structures for food policy and food security.
	Limited access to food databases (legal restrictions)	Providing access to food databases in the area of the City of Wrocław and the Wrocław Functional Area, including the location of the type of crops, logistic centers, food distribution routes, location of stores and markets.

Reflection on Broadening Process and Tools

The tools proposed by FoodCLIC allowed for the collection of knowledge, analyses, documents and information in one place. During the workshop, the FoodCLIC method from "Guidance & Inspiration" was used for complementary stakeholder mapping, which was adapted to the shape of the workshop and its participants.

Next Steps

By working together and exchanging knowledge, Wrocław was able to determine what steps we should take before the next workshop. This is primarily to invite key missing representatives of stakeholder groups to the next workshop.

5. POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS AND POTENTIAL FINANCIAL STREAMS FOR IMPLEMENTATION

The following recommendations are grounded in the insights, challenges, and emerging priorities identified by BCRs and within the Broadening process. Drawing on contributions from workshop participants and in consultation with the Think Tank, this set of recommendations thus offers a preliminary stock take of approaches that could be considered by BCR practitioners to address gaps and strengthen their engagements, while additionally giving context to consortium partners on shared challenges and their management. The recommendations are divided into seven sections:

- Strengthening Food Governance Structures and Food Policy Networks
- Including Meaningfully Actors across the Quadruple Helix
- Integrating Food Across Municipal Mandates
- Addressing Food Security and Building Resilience
- Strengthening Food Markets
- Building Community Awareness and Sensitivity
- Identifying Potential Financial Streams for Implementation

Since BCRs are in the process of finalizing their baseline assessments, the recommendations remain general and offer an initial outlook to be strengthened in the second iteration of this report once BCRs have completed their workshops. Alignment with FoodCLIC's policy framework articulated in D1.4 Advocacy Plan, learnings emerging from the LLs and recommendations captured in project policy briefs serve as additional resources to be considered. As BCRs continue with their visioning and pathway planning activities, their unique priorities will develop further. Such processes of defining their own needs and strategies first are conducive and elemental in assessing integration, support of, and alignment with national goals. Looking at alignment across policy across scales (local, regional, national, international) ensures that policies work together synergistically and that actions taken at one level support and reinforce those at other levels.

4.1 STRENGTHENING FOOD GOVERNANCE STRUCTURES AND FOOD POLICY NETWORKS

A central mechanism within the FoodCLIC project for developing integrated food policies for food systems transformation is the establishment of Food Policy Councils or networks (FPNs), which can facilitate participation across the food system from civil society, to academia, the private actor, and government. Within the Broadening process, establishing or strengthening these networks plays a crucial role in encouraging food systems transformation and the institutionalization of food systems thinking into governance structures. However, it is also important to note that only a few FPNs are truly equitable, particularly in highly unequal societies where many food system actors, such as

those in the informal sector or women, remain excluded, or where participatory processes risk crowding out agency rather than amplifying it. With this in mind, it is as crucial that the Broadening process carefully considers how to ensure that FPNs are not only representative but genuinely inclusive, particularly when led or coordinated by government officials. Of the eight BCRs, three (Fort Portal, Freiburg, and Thessaloniki) already have established more formalized food policy networks or bodies of engagements, while five (Ebolowa, eThekweni, Tbilisi, Tirana and Wrocław) are currently in the process and are working towards such goals:

- In **Fort Portal**, the Food Change Lab, spearheaded by KRC and the City Council, has laid the groundwork for systems thinking and participatory governance through advocacy platforms like the Coalition of the Willing and Orugali, which mobilize chefs, young people, vendors, and civil society around food safety and nutrition. While the city-region can already count on such well-established networks, the city is calling for these platforms to be institutionalized into a permanent, multi-sectoral food safety governance structure in order to promote coordination across departments, integrate informal sector voices, and facilitate collaboration with national agencies like the Uganda National Bureau of Standards.
- **Freiburg's Food Policy Council (Ernährungsrat)**, founded in 2018, brings together actors from farming, policy, academia, and civil society to promote sustainable and regional food practices. Getting decision-makers to endorse its strategy and make food a central topic in political governance nevertheless continues to remain a challenge. Through FoodCLIC Broadening activities, the council was nevertheless able to foster meaningful collaboration across sectors and garner support for strategic infrastructure projects such as the House of Food and the Markthalle.
- In **Thessaloniki**, the process of establishing and operating its Food Council (FC) began with an official decision by the Mayor in June 2019, marking the first of its kind to be established in Greece. The majority of the policy proposals developed by the FC aim to enhance access to nutritious, healthy, and appropriate food, ensuring food security in an integrated, less fragmented way, while bringing together actors with different roles and activities within the local food system, responding to the lack of institutional mechanisms for mediation and collaboration between the Municipality and the local community. Nevertheless, limited human and financial resources have constrained the work thus far, leading to periods of inactivity, which in turn have fostered a degree of mistrust among food systems actors. While participation in FoodCLIC has helped revive some of these efforts, it also points towards its current dependence on supra-local funds which might shift strategic directions and undermine participation in critical discussions.

Although Ebolowa, eThekweni, Tbilisi, Tirana, and Wrocław do not currently have formalized FPNs, each city-region has already taken important steps to foster food governance and cross-sector collaboration prior to its engagement in FoodCLIC and has used Broadening activities to build further on these engagements.

- In **Ebolowa**, sectoral initiatives led by national ministries such as CAPEF, MINADER, and MINEPIA have focused on strengthening local agricultural systems, including support for micro-fish farming, livestock rearing, and youth engagement in agro-entrepreneurship. These programs have contributed to building technical capacity and encouraging a new generation of food system actors. They are, however, lacking a structuring framework to avoid overlapping responsibilities.

- **eThekwini Municipality** has demonstrated longstanding commitment to food security through various sustainability and equity-focused programs, although its food strategy development process had stalled for several years due to limited institutional capacity. With the launch of FoodCLIC activities in 2024, the city has revived this process with an emphasis on participatory tools, interdepartmental collaboration, and the mapping of local food environments and initiatives. A central insight from the workshop was the recognition that certain key departments and stakeholders had been underrepresented in the preliminary planning and governance processes, whose inclusion is necessary to ensure the strategy is inclusive, holistic, and well-integrated into municipal planning frameworks. The same applies to ensuring more consistent involvement from academic institutions, NGOs, and private-sector food actors. To address this, one of the key outcomes of the workshop was a recommendation to establish a formalized multi-departmental and multi-stakeholder task team to coordinate, guide, and oversee the strategy's development and implementation.
- In **Tbilisi**, food system transformation is a relatively new area of policy focus. Efforts aligned with the city's Master Plan are currently beginning to address livability and food heritage by integrating green spaces and mixed land-use principles, and the city's primary goal for joining FoodCLIC was to establish a stakeholder forum and process, at local and national levels, that could serve as a precursor of a functional Food Policy Network (FPN). The stakeholder mapping and baseline assessment workshop served as a 'first contact' platform for many actors who had not previously collaborated, and informal partnerships emerged.
- **Tirana** has been actively engaged in initiatives aimed at transforming its food system through participation in two previous European projects, laying the groundwork for existing collaborations between diverse food systems actors and the development of a comprehensive food policy. Through FoodCLIC, it aims at building on collaborations, working on select topics including urban-rural linkages, and continuing with the development of its food policy.
- **Wrocław**, while historically less engaged in food policy, initially began exploring the topic through the Fair Local Green Deals project, which activated multi-stakeholder dialogue around food systems, food safety, and short food supply chains. Responding to growing pressures on food security, Wrocław is now taking a regional approach through collaboration with the Wrocław Functional Area - a coalition of 19 surrounding municipalities - and has designated an Urban Food Policy Coordinator.

From the brief snapshot reported above, it is clear that each BCR has already taken numerous strides towards food systems transformation prior to involvement in FoodCLIC. Building on these existing structures and initiatives through the Broadening process presents a strategic opportunity to deepen existing cross-sector collaboration, reinforce political support, and scale local innovations through more coordinated and better-resourced food policy governance. Especially this first preparatory phase revolving around stakeholder mapping and co-creation in the form of workshops has been vital, helping to build momentum and a common understanding across food systems actors of their respective food systems, its vulnerabilities and opportunities that can be leveraged on.

Examples of various approaches to structuring an effective food partnership can be found in the "[SFP Food Partnership and Strategy Toolkit](#)," recommended by the Think Tank Member Joy Carey, Senior Programme Officer at the Global Partnership on Sustainable Urban Agriculture and Food Systems (RUAFA) and, with the disclaimer that this resource is based on an EU context and primarily focused on the national scale, the recommendations by [Agora Agriculture and IDDRI \(2025\)](#) also offer a useful overview of the key steps in developing a food strategy. These include conducting a

baseline assessment, mapping stakeholders, setting shared goals through inclusive consultation, and prioritizing areas for action, feeding into concrete action plan with clear measures, timelines, and budget estimates (Agora Agriculture and IDDRI 2025: 29-31).

Finally, based on the findings of den Boer et al. (2023) in [Food policy networks and their potential to stimulate systemic intermediation for food system transformation](#) in a Dutch context, the following considerations can additionally strengthen FPNS and drive systemic, long-term change in urban food systems. The authors note that FPNs require strong, transformative leadership to coordinate diverse actors and foster cross-sector collaboration. Policymakers should also support the development of diverse and representative core groups that promote transparency and shared ownership. Ensuring structural autonomy while maintaining strategic engagement with local governments helps FPNs build legitimacy and resilience. Another key consideration, particularly relevant in contexts where food governance capacity is limited, is whether FPNs are being established to fill gaps left by state failure. If an FPN emerges because the state has not met its obligation to ensure equitable food access, it is critical to reflect on the role such a network should play: is it substituting for failed governance, legitimizing it, or holding it to account? To act as effective systemic intermediaries, FPNs must bridge across the quadruple helix, and could especially benefit from partnering with universities and adopting co-creative, transdisciplinary approaches. Underlying these considerations are stable sources of funding and institutional backing by municipalities, and the potential benefit of fostering regional collaboration through networks of networks ([Den Boer et al. 2023](#)).

4.2 INCLUDING ACTORS ACROSS THE QUADRUPLE HELIX

To enable transformative urban food policy development, it is critical to ensure inclusive, equitable, and systemic engagement with actors across the quadruple helix. Food policy transformation requires more than top-down directives; it must be co-created with the individuals and institutions it aims to serve and impact. This includes not only decision-makers and policy enablers but also stakeholder groups marginalized in policy processes, such as small-scale farmers, workers in the informal sector, residents, and community-based organizations. Participation in policy design should also reflect the cross-sectoral nature of food systems, incorporating actors from health, environment, urban planning, and waste management. This implies that while the quadruple helix approach seeks to foster inclusion and participation, it is important to reflect critically on its limitations. Simply adding civil society actors to those in the existing three other sectors does not automatically equate to meaningful inclusion. It is important for FPNs to consider whether the inclusion of marginalized persons also ensures that power dynamics are accounted for and that they have a meaningful voice in the process. As findings from Food Policy Networks (FPNs) in Europe and beyond suggest, building and maintaining a diverse and engaged core group remains a persistent challenge, particularly in reaching minority groups and large-scale private actors (Den Boer et al. 2023). This underscores the urgency of embedding deliberate, context-sensitive strategies to include and connect all relevant voices in the policy-making continuum.

Enhancing Participation of People Marginalized by Societal and Food Systems Inequities

For those BCRs that already have a food policy body or network in place, one priority is to strengthen it by including currently underrepresented actors - particularly vulnerable and food-deprived groups,

defined by FoodCLIC as “people whose diets are lacking in quantity or nutritional quality on account of limited access as a result of spatiality, living on low income and/or personal circumstances” (Grant Agreement 2022). Vulnerable groups can include food deprived individuals, small-scale farmers and workers in agriculture, people in a situation of houselessness, children and adults living in food poverty, marginalized and/or racialized migrants and refugees, and individuals living with health conditions, among others. Despite being clustered under ‘vulnerable and food-deprived’ also in this report, these groups, and people within these groups, are not homogenous and it is essential to understand their distinct challenges and tailor engagement strategies accordingly, in addition to acknowledging their agency and role as crucial partners in fostering up bottom-up approaches. Vulnerabilities are often not inherent and rather produced by injustice in our society and our food system.

- In **Wrocław**, the ongoing war in Ukraine has heightened food security concerns, particularly for Ukrainian refugees, alongside other groups such as flood victims, socially excluded youth, elderly people, and those experiencing houselessness or poverty. In Broadening activities of the city, especially the importance of gaining access to reliable data, was emphasized to effectively map and engage these communities.
- In **Ebolowa**, inclusivity also remains a challenge, with women and young people often being unable to access available support structures, and small-scale farmers and informal vendors, despite their essential role in the food system, lacking political influence and representation in decision-making forums.
- **eThekwini** also noted the limited involvement of informal traders and traditional leaders in food-related governance, even though they hold valuable local knowledge and play key roles in enabling food access.
- In **Tirana**, marginalized groups including smallholder farmers, migrant labourers, and low-income consumers are often not present in discussions, not because of a lack of interest on their end, but in difficulties in reaching them, and accessibility of such spaces. Some also do not perceive themselves as stakeholders in these processes, further limiting their engagement.

While the role of underrepresented actors as crucial partners in fostering bottom-up approaches is recognized, their limited availability often makes meaningful engagement difficult. As a result, engagement sometimes happens indirectly, e.g. through food banks when it comes to engagement with food-deprived people, which can result in misaligned interests. As Think Tank member Gareth Haysom, researcher at the African Centre for Cities (ACC), pointed out during one of the project Think Tank exchanges, this is not just a limitation, but a broader systemic reality. He emphasized the need to actively confront this challenge, noting that finding ways to overcome it is essential to making food system processes genuinely inclusive and impactful. As such, based on the motivations of Ebolowa, eThekwini, and Wrocław to engage more meaningfully with groups that require more effort to reach, procedural recommendations for facilitating their participation in food policy arena include providing stipends or honoraria for lived-experience experts, offering logistical support (e.g., meals, transport, flexible timings) for meetings, setting meeting spaces that are convenient and accessible, ensuring cultural and linguistic sensitivity in all engagements and facilitating skill sharing for long-term community empowerment.

Engaging the Private Sector Strategically

In addition to the challenge of including persons made vulnerable, another challenge lies in the inclusion of for-profit entities, which often hold significant influence over key levers of food systems change. Furthermore, power imbalances between these actors also complicate equitable collaboration. It is therefore important to differentiate among private sector actors based on their size, type, and the nature of their profit-making activities. Research has shown that certain private sector actors - particularly large food industry representatives and retailers - have, at times, hindered or delayed the adoption and implementation of public health-oriented food policies, such as sugar-sweetened beverage taxes and nutrition or environmental labelling. This underscores the need to be mindful and strategic when engaging with such actors, ensuring that their involvement aligns with broader goals of public good and food system transformation (Agora Agriculture & IDDRI, 2025, 25).

The city of **Thessaloniki**, for example, has the goal of working towards more meaningful engagement with the hospitality and tourism sector, including hotels and restaurants, due to having identified key opportunities for fostering co-benefits of sustainability with this sector. This ambition builds on its recent expansion of the municipal food agenda beyond gastronomy and fragmented social measures to a broader, strategic approach, supported by international networking. Furthermore, joining UNESCO's Creative Cities Network for Gastronomy in 2021 has created strong links with the local hospitality and tourism industries, positioning them as active partners in promoting sustainable food systems. To effectively involve businesses and foster buy-in, it is indeed important to understand their motivations, identify what makes participation valuable to them, such as opportunities for cost savings and alignment with corporate social responsibility (CSR) goals, and possible barriers of implementation. Drawing on examples from other cities can also offer practical insights into successful models of private sector engagement.

Collaborating with Academia

Academic partnerships can play a catalytic role by supporting evidence-based policymaking, facilitating inclusive dialogue, and nurturing long-term innovations grounded in both theory and practice. Strengthening ties between food policy networks (FPNs) and higher education and research institutions can enhance access to resources and foster connections with complementary programs that share the goal of advancing integrated food policies and systemic food transformation (Den Boer et al. 2023). While all BCRs can benefit from further strengthening such collaborations, two in particular have already established such partnerships:

- A key driving force in **Fort Portal**'s food systems transformation, for example, has been its longstanding partnership with the Kabarole Research and Resource Centre (KRC). By working closely with Fort Portal City Council, KRC played a pivotal role in shaping the city's food governance, most notably through the creation of the Food Change Lab, a multi-year process that brought together diverse stakeholders to develop practical, community-driven solutions for healthier and more equitable food systems. Partnering with a research center offered the city the necessary deep technical expertise in food and nutrition, grounded community connections, and the possibility to facilitate participatory research. This kind of collaboration not only enhances local capacity but also ensures that interventions such as the creation of the city-wide food safety strategy, are rooted in real-world needs and perspectives, ultimately leading to more resilient and responsive urban food systems.

- The Broadening Process in the city of **Freiburg** also underscores how through collaborations with academia, city-regions can gain access to scientific expertise, independent research capacity, and a pipeline of motivated students eager to apply their knowledge to real-world challenges. Freiburg's first Broadening workshop was co-organized with a seminar class led by Prof. Stephan Lengsfeld from the Institute of Finance, Controlling & Entrepreneurship at the University of Freiburg. As part of their coursework, the seminar students previously conducted interviews with stakeholders to develop a business concept applicable to the Market Hall project. Although the seminar concluded in February 2025, the students expressed a strong interest in continuing their work on the project. In response, a new seminar was created to further develop the concept and conduct additional research on sustainable market halls. This co-creative process involving students, practitioners, and researchers added both depth and legitimacy to the initiative, underscoring the value of cross-generational and interdisciplinary collaboration.

4.3 INTEGRATING FOOD ACROSS MUNICIPAL MANDATES

Urban food systems intersect with a wide range of municipal mandates beyond traditional food policy, including urban planning, health, housing and social services, public health, climate action, and circular economy initiatives. As a result, multiple departments within city administrations influence how food-related activities - from food safety to food waste - are governed. To enable more coherent and supportive food systems, local governments must prioritize cross-departmental coordination and policy integration within municipal structures.

Formulating an integrated food policy from scratch can be daunting for municipal policy-makers, especially in cases where there is little or no funding available and interdepartmental coordination is weak or lacking. A critical first step in this process is to map existing policies, institutional competencies, and departmental responsibilities. This helps identify synergies, uncover regulatory gaps or overlaps, and remove barriers that food actors, such as market vendors or food recovery initiatives, may face when interfacing with municipal systems. Many of the BCRs conducted an inventory of existing food policies, strategies, planning frameworks, and food initiatives during their first workshop as a starting point.

- In the city of **Ebolowa**, although there is already an existing structured network of interactions that involve public institutions, producers' associations, traders, and regulatory bodies, a formalized structure such as a Food Policy Council is not yet in place to coordinate the differentiated often overlapping mandates across departments. During the workshop, participants mapped out the shared mandates of the local government and relevant institutions. For example, waste and environmental management involves both HYSACAM (a private company managing municipal waste) and municipal services, while the food flow regulations fall under the Ministry of Trade, working in collaboration with customs and law enforcement agencies.
- In **eThekwini**, the city prioritized interdepartmental collaboration during their initial workshop. A major takeaway was the realization that several important departments and stakeholders had been overlooked in early planning and governance efforts, limiting their

integration into municipal frameworks. Similarly, there was a need for more consistent engagement from academic institutions, NGOs, and private-sector food actors. To tackle these gaps, the workshop recommended creating a formal multi-departmental and multi-stakeholder task team to coordinate, guide, and oversee the development and implementation of the strategy. Think Tank member Gareth Haysom adds that in addition to departments themselves, departmental budget holders making budget decision must be included in such processes: for discussions and agreements to be actioned, those that have the tools and authority to ensure action need to be in the room.

To optimize these collaborations, it is essential that policy engagement and integration occur both horizontally (i.e., between municipal governments) and vertically (from civil society to municipal to state, national and international levels). This may entail the use of novel governance mechanisms, such as the appointment of a food policy officer as is the case in the city of **Wrocław**, as well as active negotiations with higher levels of governance around key issues and common challenges.

As next steps to support more integrated governance, cities can establish cross-departmental steering committees, embed food policy goals into city master plans and budgeting processes, and explore synergies with climate adaptation and mitigation goals, such as promoting urban agriculture and reducing food waste. The Food Council of **Thessaloniki** has recognized the importance of such integration of food with other goals and in its particular case, connecting it with climate neutrality to foster synergies, as climate change is one of its biggest challenges. As such, the upcoming update of the city's climate contract for instance presents a crucial opportunity to integrate the food policy angle further into city-planning, and its Broadening work has supported building a baseline and getting actors together.

Such approaches lay the groundwork for integrated food policies that “unite numerous food-related actions across other policy domains and sectors” (Ferne et al. 2024, 1). By addressing fragmented governance and overcoming “siloization”, such approaches promote cross-sectoral collaboration, innovation, and inclusivity (Tosun & Lang 2017). When led by municipalities, integrated food policies can unlock co-benefits across health, economy, and environment, forge linkages between rural and urban areas by partnering with diverse institutions and local actors, promote inclusion by bringing underrepresented groups into decision-making processes, and enhance connectivity across policy areas (e.g., food, climate, education), fostering resilience and continuity. In doing so, they contribute to building resilient, inclusive, and sustainable urban food systems that are fully aligned with broader city development goals including climate resilience, social justice, and economic development.

4.4 ADDRESSING FOOD SECURITY AND BUILDING RESILIENCE

Although an underlying consideration in all cities, eThekweni, Fort Portal and Wrocław have explicitly listed food security, affordability and nutrition as priority topics to be addressed as part of their FoodCLIC Broadening processes.

- In **eThekwini** workshops participants highlighted the existence of hunger especially among children, and challenges for parents trying to feed their children healthy meals, linked to the unequal distribution of access to nutritious food.
- Despite being located in a highly productive agricultural region, **Fort Portal** also faces high levels of food insecurity and malnutrition. One key reason found was the range of biological, chemical, and physical risks in the current food environment, including unsafe food handling, lack of proper sanitation, pesticide misuse, and limited infrastructure, such as cold storage or clean water.
- In **Wrocław**, food security has been noted as a regional challenge especially in the context of drought, flooding and supply chain disruptions, as fueled by the Covid-19 pandemic in 2020 and the refugee crisis in 2022 related to the war in Ukraine.

Possible policy responses at a more basic level to improve accessibility, affordability and general food provisioning thus include strengthening data collection on food insecurity at local levels to inform action, supporting infrastructure providing free meals, e.g. in schools, communicating about offerings in multiple languages in contexts where vulnerability and migration status intersect, regulating fair pricing policies and subsidizing shops and restaurants, and generally supporting access to food infrastructure, e.g. in the form of mobile markets. Further, food security should also be promoted by focusing specifically on poverty-reduction and empowerment, through the fostering of food entrepreneurship, livelihood development, and capacity building programs.

As food security has also been influenced by inequities linked to globalized value chain, trade and interconnected risks across national boundaries, **Ebolowa** in particular has also emphasized the aspect of the promotion of regional self-sufficiency as opposed to relying on imported food items. Workshop participants mentioned that this would involve actively promoting agricultural and livestock production within the region and encouraging local food sourcing to ensure a stable and accessible food supply. A key strategy discussed was also to support entrepreneurship of young people in the agricultural sector, which would not only revitalize the rural economy, but also foster innovation and long-term investment in food production. Moreover, local governments should collaborate closely with national authorities to accelerate the implementation of import-substitution policies, as seen in Cameroon's recent national strategy promoting domestic production. This multi-level, collective approach is essential for enhancing urban food security and fostering economic resilience by anchoring food systems more firmly within local and regional contexts.

4.5 STRENGTHENING FOOD MARKETS

Several BCRs have identified strengthening of local food markets as a key priority within the project.

- **Fort Portal** has highlighted the lack of infrastructure, such as cold storage and hygiene measures, as a major contributor to low food safety.
- In **Ebolowa**, the need to improve market infrastructure emerged as a critical issue during the field visit, due to significant deficiencies in waste management and energy access, which directly impact the organization of vendors and compromise the safety and quality of food products.

- **Tbilisi** aims to transform its informal farmers' market at the Railway Station into a socially just and inclusive hub.
- **Tirana** seeks to improve the distribution of farmers' markets and better integrate small-scale producers into municipal systems.

Together, these examples underscore the central role food markets play in shaping equitable, safe, and accessible urban food environments.

Food markets sit at the intersection of urban and rural food systems, making them a vital entry point for strengthening territorial linkages. They are critical for local food security, nutrition, and resilience, providing spaces for diverse, healthy, and often affordable food options. Markets also offer economic opportunities to small-scale farmers and vendors, who may otherwise be excluded from corporate supply chains. By stabilizing prices, shortening supply chains, and giving communities greater agency over their food systems, well-managed local markets can become powerful tools for sustainable urban development.

To strengthen the integration of small-scale producers, particularly women, youth, and local communities, into food systems, it is essential to build their capacity to access markets through support for cooperatives, associations, and producer networks. Promoting enterprise and entrepreneurship can further enhance their bargaining power and participation in value chains. In parallel, public procurement programs - such as school meals or food distribution systems - should prioritize locally produced foods and smallholder suppliers (FAO 2025).

Local governments can improve food market infrastructure through investments, permitting, partnerships, and access to services such as roads, lighting, waste management, and digital platforms that connect producers and consumers. Insufficient storage, roofing, and WASH (Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene) facilities can lead to food loss and waste, and municipalities can address these by facilitating infrastructure upgrades such as cold storage, drainage, and solar-powered stalls. Many cities promote organic waste separation and composting for urban agriculture, as in many cases, organic waste often makes up a large proportion of overall waste in food markets.

4.6 BUILDING COMMUNITY AWARENESS AND SENSITIVITY

To ensure the effective implementation of food safety regulations, **Fort Portal** has identified the increase of public awareness and capacity building as part of their food safety strategy as a priority. Regulations alone are insufficient without widespread community buy-in and engagement, so one of the city's foci should be to invest in behavior change communication campaigns that are culturally relevant and accessible (e.g. by using local languages, audio-visual formats, and trusted community-led platforms such as the Orugali network). Youth-led initiatives and civil society organizations have proven effective in raising awareness and should be further empowered to lead local outreach. In parallel, targeted capacity-building for informal food actors is essential. Training on hygiene, food handling, and pesticide use will not only reduce risks but also promote equity across the food

system. Finally, successful models like care groups (which equip one community member to train 15 neighboring households) could be scaled up as effective examples of peer-to-peer learning.

Similarly, one of the key findings of **Tirana's** stakeholder mapping and baseline assessments was a limited initial awareness of actors and participation in food system discussions. Participants, particularly those in the business sector and civil society, were unfamiliar with food systems thinking or did not immediately see how FoodCLIC activities might be beneficial. To address this, a participative communication approach was used, engaging local multipliers including municipal officials, schools, and community leaders to spread the word, and employing storytelling to connect abstract ideas to lived realities, like food (in)access. On a broader level of building awareness on the importance of food systems, programs in Tirana aimed at the younger generation, including teaching students to reduce their food waste and adopt healthier eating habits, have already been showing positive results. As participants stressed, there is a particular opportunity of such campaigns to address health risks associated with foodborne illnesses, chronic diseases, and the vulnerability of children and elderly populations in the context of climate and lifestyle changes. As such, recommendations included further integrating early nutrition education into school programs, public awareness campaigns on food hygiene, labeling, and preparation and institutional and media support to improve healthy food choices.

4.7 IDENTIFYING POTENTIAL FINANCIAL STREAMS FOR IMPLEMENTATION

Access to finance is a critical enabler for cities seeking to implement food system transformation initiatives. While the FoodCLIC Broadening process supports essential activities such as stakeholder mapping, baseline assessments, visioning, and strategic pathway development, it does not provide the level of financial support required to operationalize many of the concrete actions that city-regions are ready to pursue. Even at this early stage, several BCRs have identified specific needs and project ideas, ranging from infrastructure development to support small-scale farmers. However, they often lack the necessary resources to implement them. Others are focused on maintaining momentum and bringing food system actors together, deepening capacity through training, coordination, and governance efforts. Without sustained financing, these important processes risk stagnating just as they begin to take root.

The mapping and assessments that were conducted in this phase provide valuable insight into the types of financial support required.

- Food systems actors in **Ebolowa** have identified critical infrastructure deficiencies, such as poor roads, outdated markets and slaughterhouses, and a lack of modern food processing units as significant barriers to a resilient and productive food system. Local actors stress the importance of mobilizing financial resources through partnerships with institutions like FEICOM (Special Council Support Fund for Mutual Assistance - financial institution serving regional and local authorities in Cameroon) and local banks, with a particular emphasis on financing equipment and strengthening local production.

- **eThekwini** points to the need for funds to support small-scale farmers, including financial literacy training and enabling broader financial access. The city also made note that its progress toward a food strategy - which had been in discussions for four years prior - was largely able to be revived through support from the FoodCLIC project, underlining the importance of financing also to support food systems governance structures more generally.
- In **Fort Portal**, upgrading informal food market infrastructure is a top priority. Investments in clean water, cold storage, waste management, and hygiene facilities are seen as critical for food safety, public health, and sustainable livelihoods.
- **Freiburg** has proposed establishing a “House of Food,” a physical food hub to fuel food entrepreneurship, that could be supported through national funding schemes or alternative approaches like crowdfunding.
- **Tbilisi** has signaled a desire to improve informal food markets, though the specific financial needs are less defined at this stage.
- In **Thessaloniki**, the effectiveness of its Food Council is heavily influenced by its lack of resources, leading to long periods of inactivity, damaging the trust and cooperation relationships among FPC members, and consequently negatively affecting their level of participation. More sustainable funding is needed to address these challenges and also reduce dependencies, so that Thessaloniki can work towards addressing local needs as opposed to catering to supra-local agendas.
- Meanwhile, though no single flagship initiative has been articulated within these cities yet, **Tirana** has voiced commitments to enhancing alliances between grassroots actors and legislators, through capacity building, improving accessibility of policy spaces, and the use of participatory budgeting. **Wrocław** has identified a broad array of opportunities in its SWOT analysis, such as awareness-raising and education, supporting small-scale agriculture and building its food policy network to strengthen food systems resilience especially in times of crisis, for which funding would be vital.

If the existing municipal internal revenue sources (e.g. property tax, land fees, service charges) are insufficient to fund priority initiatives, local governments may need to turn to external sources. These can include national government transfers, loans, or support from international development institutions and regional entities such as the European Commission as part of broader aid or investment packages.

Larger infrastructure projects typically rely on a mix of financial streams. These may include blended finance coming from multiple sources to reduce investment risk and crowd in additional funding (most commonly combining concessional capital from development finance institutions and commercial capital, with philanthropic funds coming in for technical assistance), and alternative finance instruments such as social impact bonds, cooperative investment models, or community-supported funding mechanisms.

In addition, public-private partnerships (PPPs) may also be utilized for funding food systems work in contexts with enabling governance and regulatory frameworks. Through long-term agreements, cities can partner with private sector actors to co-develop and operate infrastructure or services, such as cold storage facilities or waste management systems which serve public goals, while leveraging private expertise and capital. Nevertheless, barriers at the local level exist, especially in situations where municipalities have limited capacity to structure, enforce, and supervise complex PPP contracts, or contexts when the domestic private sector lacks the financial resources to engage in long-term projects. PPPs themselves also come with inherent risks, including the potential for

misaligned priorities, reduced public control over essential services, and long-term financial obligations that may further strain municipal budgets. These risks should be carefully managed through well-structured, clear and accountable frameworks, equitable risk-sharing, and strong public oversight to ensure they serve the interests of the broader community. It is particularly important to note that particularly in resource-constrained contexts, PPP implementation faces additional barriers: a limited capacity within municipalities to structure, enforce, and supervise complex PPP contracts; a domestic private sector that lacks the financial resources to engage in long-term infrastructure projects; and high transaction costs and elevated risks, which reduce private sector appetite. For food system interventions, such as investments in cold storage or market facilities, these challenges are even more pronounced, making PPPs difficult to justify without complementary support, reinforcing high transaction costs and risks.

Given the limitations many cities face, particularly of legally not being able to access (international) finance and a limited in-house capacity to navigate the complex processes required to access such fundings, approaching suitable funders requires a nuanced and well-prepared strategy. Several global initiatives support local and regional governments, especially in low and middle-income economies, in accessing international capitals. ICLEI's [Transformative Actions Program \(TAP\)](#), for instance, provides advisory and light-touch technical assistance for cities to structure robust and financeable sustainable urban infrastructure projects and navigate project preparation and financing. The [City Climate Finance Gap Fund](#) offers assistance for the development of strategies and the development of pre-feasibility studies for resilient low-carbon projects, including food markets. UN-Habitat's [Cities Investment Facility \(CIF\)](#), in turn, provides funding for feasibility studies and financing through a blended finance fund. Another blended finance facility, the [Subnational Climate Fund \(SCF\)](#), combines resources from the Green Climate Fund (GCF) and private investors to support technical assistance and investment in food systems and sustainable agriculture initiatives. Equally supported by the GCF, the [World Food Programme](#) has several projects that support smallholder farmers and food security in Africa and Asia. In the European context, the European Urban Initiative (EUI), co-funded by the European Union, supports urban authorities across the EU in developing and testing innovative solutions to pressing urban challenges. In Africa, the African Development Bank-supported ARCH Cold Chain Solutions East Africa Fund (CCSEAF) supports cities by expanding temperature-controlled storage and logistics for urban food markets.

For a more detailed overview of financing trends and alternative financing mechanisms, including their strategic uses and benefits, cities are encouraged to consult FoodCLIC Project Deliverable [D5.5 Short report on most valid food-related exploitation schemes](#) created by Cariplo, which offers a structured breakdown of options aligned with food system goals.

Whatever the project may be, it is crucial for funding decisions, especially in complex, multi-stakeholder food systems, to be guided by transparency, collective decision-making and a strong commitment to equity. Investors are increasingly prioritizing initiatives that are cross-cutting and ambitious, those that advance multiple SDGs, demonstrate clear climate impacts (particularly on resilience and adaptation), are gender-responsive, foster a just transition and create jobs. Urban policy makers should therefore ensure that projects are designed to be sustainable, inclusive, and transformative, aligning them with community priorities and capturing the attention of potential investors.

Marginalized groups, who are disproportionately affected by food system inequities, should be given greater weight in funding-related deliberations. While a pragmatic approach is necessary, particularly

in resource-constrained contexts, participatory processes should govern all major funding choices to ensure legitimacy, equity, and long-term impact. Collaborative bodies such as FPNs can add value here, granted that they actively work to address power dynamics and elevate voices of civil society and city-region residents.

Finally, a note of caution: when exploring financial streams for urban food system interventions, it is essential to avoid assumptions that the complexities of food environments are fully understood or that existing urban agriculture initiatives sufficiently address the complexity of food system challenges. As Think Tank Member Gareth Haysom highlighted in his feedback following the Berlin meeting (October 2024), in many African cities, for example, local governments have limited or no formal mandate over food systems, leading to fragmented, siloed, and often short-term project-based responses rather than integrated system-level interventions. A common but problematic trend is the constant deference to urban agriculture projects by city governments which implies a one-size-fits-all solution overlooking the core issue of food access and the need for projects with a long-term vision and support behind them. Evidence from projects such as AfriFOODlinks shows a disconnect between city-led project choices and the actual needs of food-insecure populations; for example, in Windhoek, only 3% of vulnerable respondents viewed gardening as a viable solution, yet it was the primary intervention selected. This highlights the critical need for comprehensive food system analysis and an inclusive governance mechanism to guide decision-making. City-regions also require support to foster collaboration across government departments and, crucially, to develop strategies for sharing limited fiscal resources. Without this strategic and informed approach, financial investments risk reinforcing ineffective solutions rather than enabling systemic change.

6. CONCLUSION

Summary of Key Contributions and Findings

The first round of FoodCLIC Broadening workshops conducted across the eight BCRs served as an important step in bundling and revitalizing existing efforts for food systems transformation through participatory, context-driven processes. Despite differences in geography, institutional maturity and levels of technical support, several shared themes and lessons emerged. Across all cities, the workshops brought together diverse actors, government departments, civil society, private sector, academia, and marginalized voices to engage in structured dialogue around food system transformation, building shared understanding and trust, laying (or in some cases reinforcing) the groundwork for longer-term cooperation.

Throughout the stakeholder mapping and baseline assessment workshops, BCRs effectively used participatory tools, some also directly coming from FoodCLIC guidelines, such as the inclusivity scan template and initiative mappings to unpack the complexity of their food systems. These tools proved helpful not only in identifying missing actors and co-benefits, but also in fostering a systemic understanding of local challenges and opportunities. Interesting to note is that even food policy councils and food governance structures that have existed for some time identified missing actors during this process. This raises important reflections for the process: Why were these actors previously excluded, and what does this reveal about how such governance processes operate? Do some stakeholders know about these structures but choose not to participate, and if so, what could be done to engage them? Could this call into question the representativeness of certain FPNs, and might some benefit from creating sub-units or alternative engagement mechanisms to broaden participation? These reflections are important for encouraging governance structures to examine how inclusive and adaptive they truly are, we encourage BCRs to actively consider these questions in their own processes.

Workshops in eThekweni, Ebolowa, Fort Portal and Tirana for instance revealed underrepresentation of small-scale producers, informal vendors, youth, women, and socially vulnerable groups and underscored the need for explicit strategies to incorporate their voices and perspectives. In the case of Thessaloniki, workshop participants also noted the necessity, but also difficulties of involving civil society, linking these to suspicions towards institutions and project-based actions. In Wrocław and eThekweni, SWOT analyses were instrumental in assessing strategic positioning and vulnerability, while Tbilisi used the Power Tree template directly coming from FoodCLIC's suite of tools to map root causes, system dynamics, and transformative actions to improve its food system. Another key FoodCLIC insight validated by BCRs was the critical importance of grounding food policy in the lived realities of residents. eThekweni and Fort Portal, for example, made strong use of participatory mapping exercises in field visits to various food environments to integrate community voices, such as through the use of an adapted Whatsapp voice mapping of reflections. This helped highlight the disconnect between top-down planning and local experiences, especially regarding food access, safety, affordability, and cultural relevance, calling for greater sensitivity to context and equity. In terms of challenges, fragmented governance and siloed mandates was another cross-cutting issue several cities identified as a universal concern. City-regions like Tbilisi, Tirana and Wrocław, for example, expressed the need for structured coordination mechanisms, such as interdepartmental working groups or formal food policy councils. Meanwhile cities such as Fort Portal, Freiburg,

Thessaloniki and Wrocław, which already had more developed networks, used the workshops to further establish and strengthen their structures and influence.

Thus, this first round of FoodCLIC Broadening workshops confirmed that systemic transformation starts with a shared understanding of the food system that actors are living in, and by building alliances across the spectrum. By using participatory methods to map stakeholders, power dynamics, and local realities, BCRs have taken critical steps toward inclusive, actionable, and resilient food strategies. The challenge ahead is to build on this foundation by strengthening collaborations and governance mechanisms, deepening analysis, co-designing visions and roadmaps that are both locally grounded and globally informed.

Overall Reflections

A key factor in the success of the Broadening process so far was the strong emphasis on co-creation and the flexible use of tools, which allowed the approach to be adapted to each BCR's unique context while navigating technical and financial constraints. This flexibility was reinforced by the strategic adoption and adaptation of tools developed in the pilot city-regions. Rather than applying them uniformly, these tools were used selectively, based on their relevance, practicality, and alignment with each city-region's specific priorities, ensuring that the overall approach remained both grounded and locally responsive. Given that each BCR operates within a unique setting, often influenced by political shifts, administrative changes, and the advancement of parallel initiatives, ensuring a flexible and tailor-made approach of the Broadening process was necessary. Only by ensuring that level of flexibility, it was possible to support city-regions in integrating FoodCLIC priorities in ways that complemented their existing goals and realities. To make the framework more accessible, efforts were made to simplify both the language and structure of the process, recognizing that most city-regions involved were not represented by research institutions. This tailored approach was well received, resulting in a diverse and locally grounded process across the BCRs.

Over the past months, reflections also emerged around specific project design choices. One key point concerned the geographical distribution of BCRs, with some suggesting a more balanced representation between Africa and Europe (4 and 4, rather than 3 and 5). Another related to the allocation of implementation funds, with a call to support Living Lab activities also in BCRs. While significant progress was made despite limited resources, dedicated budgets for implementation could have further supported local efforts and strengthened the replicability of the model. Although these elements were to be considered in the initial project design and budget allocation and thus cannot be changed in due course, they highlight areas for refinement in future initiatives.

Another such consideration and learning from this Broadening process for future initiatives is that the expansion of peer-to-peer exchange and broadening project learning beyond Europe can significantly strengthen the Horizon Europe projects in addressing the global challenges of food systems, climate change, and sustainable urban development. Engaging with cities from other regions enables the sharing of diverse perspectives, knowledge systems, methods and governance approaches with the European counterparts. Non-European cities can in fact also benefit from methods and tools developed by the project, and while tools may not be directly transferable, they can inspire locally adapted solutions as the FoodCLIC Broadening process as shown. This type of exchange not only enriches the methodology but also encourages critical reflection on embedded structures within Europe, acknowledging their global influence and historical context. Future projects

would benefit from designing dedicated funding mechanisms to support such inclusive, globally relevant collaborations.

An additional concern that emerged relates to the use of specific terminology within the project. While terms such as “exploitation” and “stakeholder” are commonly used and often treated as neutral, their historical and political connotations, particularly in contexts involving African city-regions, warrant careful reflection. The term “exploitation”, though standard in EU project language, has been flagged as potentially inappropriate due to its colonial and extractive implications. As a project committed to transformation and equity, there is an opportunity to lead by example and consider alternative, more inclusive terminology where possible. Similarly, the term “stakeholder” has prompted critical reflection on power dynamics within food systems. It implies equal participation yet often masks structural inequalities and disproportionately amplifies voices with greater resources, particularly from the private sector. Applying the recent HLPE (2024) term of “multi-actor groups” helps reflect the diversity of actors involved and acknowledge the need to center actors least served by the system, those who should be the ones with the greatest leverage to change the system. Another key point is recognizing that vulnerability is not inherent but often produced by centuries of long-standing inequalities. These realities call for careful reflection and greater accountability in participatory processes. Key questions must be addressed, such as: How are the actors influencing policy decisions selected, and what backgrounds do they represent? Whose voices are being prioritized in shaping new policy solutions and interventions? Multi-stakeholder platforms are often presented as neutral, yet they are inherently political spaces shaped by unequal power relations. Transparency in actor selection and a clear understanding of local political dynamics are therefore critical.

A final note of caution concerns the comparison and exchange of food environment frameworks between markedly different contexts, particularly between African and European city-regions. While predefined food environment categories may provide a useful starting point, they risk overlooking critical elements that are fundamental in the African context. Key features of African urban food systems, such as the key role of informal traders, the connections to transport and infrastructure, the prevalence of large-scale food advertising, poor water quality that drives the consumption of sugar-sweetened beverages, and the significance of wet markets, are often underrepresented or ignored. This leads to a misrepresentation, as the role of micro-, small-, and medium-sized enterprises (MSMEs) is frequently omitted in such frameworks. These enterprises are not just peripheral actors but represent the backbone of city-region food systems in Africa. As Gareth Haysom pointed out, “MSMEs are by far the majority of the private sector in agri-food value chains on the continent,” making their inclusion in any mapping or analysis essential. Current food environment frameworks tend to be scale- and infrastructure-agnostic and often disregard the dynamic and interconnected nature of food systems. In many African cities, food purchasing behaviors shift significantly with the seasons and even throughout the month. As such, a one-off or static mapping process is unlikely to capture the full picture. Mapping can still be valuable, but it should be combined with local knowledge and complementary methods to reflect these dynamic patterns. Finally, food systems do not exist in isolation. Most food environment frameworks fail to account for the influence of other systems. Any mapping or analytical tool must therefore be designed to capture these cross-sectoral linkages and reflect how power is exercised and experienced across the food environment.

Next Steps in the Broadening Process and a Snapshot of the Second Progress Report

As the FoodCLIC Broadening process moves into its next phase, the focus will shift toward strategic planning and long-term visioning. The upcoming progress report will capture city-regions' work on Steps 6 through 8 of the FoodCLIC methodology: developing a long-term vision for their food systems, identifying context-specific pathways for change, and agreeing on priorities, timelines, roles, and resource needs. Building on the foundational work of stakeholder mapping and baseline assessments, this next stage will further consolidate local ownership and inform the co-creation of actionable, inclusive food strategies.

Looking ahead, the second progress report (D5.12, due August 2026), will reflect on evolving political contexts, continued peer-to-peer learning, and progress toward locally grounded implementation frameworks, with a particular focus on visioning and the articulation of pathways of change. These reflections will help ensure that local efforts remain adaptable, inclusive, and aligned with the project's overarching goal of fostering resilient and integrated urban food systems across diverse city-regions.

7. ANNEX

Annex 1: FoodCLIC Broadening City-Region Selection Process and Ranking

At the Think Tank meeting in Lisbon in September 2023, experts advised on a draft set of selection criteria for Broadening city-regions, which were used to design a selection process and public [‘call for participation’](#). Through an online application form, city-regions applying to FoodCLIC’s Broadening activities were asked to demonstrate, amongst others:

- A **clear intention to work on urban food governance**, showing that urban food governance and transformation is a priority in their political agenda – for example, through the inclusion of food in existing strategies/ projections or existing initiatives.
- **Interest in food system transformation** and the **relevance of FoodCLIC’s process** for the city-region, as evidenced by local/ urban, climate, environmental and social challenges, as well as by relevant strategies and activities across scales (local, regional, national).
- **Commitment to, and political support** for, working on food system issues and developing local food policies and/or programs and initiation of some related activities (even if preliminary).
- **Existing experience with and/or the ability to mobilise food systems stakeholders** across sectors present in the city-region (private, public, and academic) and across scales (local, regional, national).
- Status of or willingness to consider, where appropriate, creating a formal Food Policy Network (FPN), namely a **multi-stakeholder body focusing on food system policies, activities, and initiatives**.
- Capacity and willingness to dedicate **appropriate staff time** and engage with FoodCLIC to co-organise three local workshops/events based on FoodCLIC’s process.
- Interest and willingness to engage in **peer-to-peer learning activities** and national and international events.
- Ability of city-region representatives to communicate in **English** as the project’s primary working language.

The call officially closed on March 15th, 2024, and in total, 50 applications were received. The selection committee at ICLEI used the selection criteria to rank applications and create a shortlist of city-regions (Rank A) to be reviewed by the consortium and the Think Tank for final selection:

Cities from Africa	Cities from Europe
Rank A (City-regions shortlisted for further deliberation)	
Lusaka, Zambia	Freiburg, Germany
Kisumu, Kenya	Tbilisi, Georgia
eThekweni, Durban, South Africa	Thessaloniki, Greece
Fort Portal Tourism City, Uganda	Tirana, Albania
Lomé (Commune Golfe 2), Togo	Rome, Italy
Harare, Zimbabwe	Wroclaw, Poland
Ebolowa, Cameroon	

Gauteng City Region, South Africa	
Jinja City, Uganda	
Northern Uganda, Uganda	
Tamale Metropolitan Assembly Northern Region, Ghana	
South-East Africa, Malawi	
Rank B	
City of Douala, Cameroon	Lleida, Spain
Mbita Municipality, Kenya	Bergamo, Italy
Ibadan, Nigeria	Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina
Eastern Region, Ghana	Adana, Turkey
Nakuru, Kenya	Minho Region, Portugal
Antananarivo, Madagascar	Maastricht, Netherlands
Bukavu, Democratic Republic of Congo	Hof, Germany
Sekondi-Takoradi, Western Ghana	Nuoro, Italy
Kombo East District, The Gambia	Fermanagh and Omagh, United Kingdom
Accra, Ghana	Ghent, Belgium
Kampala, Uganda	Póvoa de Varzim, Portugal
Entebbe, Uganda	Wageningen-Ede, The Netherlands
Togoville, Togo	
City of uMhlathuze, South Africa	
KwaZulu- Natal, South Africa	
Kigali, Rwanda	
Rank C (Applications excluded due to incompleteness or failure to meet criteria)	
Seven excluded applications	

Annex 2: FoodCLIC Broadening Preparation – Initial Goals, Challenges, Existing Assessments and Initiatives and Priorities for Phase 1

City-Region	Webinar Component	Feedback
Ebolowa	FoodCLIC Process Goals	<p>Building blocks for developing a coherent food systems approach (sustainable food policy for the next decade) through policy integration, horizontal integration across municipal departments, and connecting of stakeholders across the quadruple helix</p> <p>Focus on mapping and defining power dynamics of stakeholders.</p> <p>Raising awareness on the value and importance of food systems</p> <p>#StakeholderEngagement #PolicyIntegration #HorizontalIntegration #ActionPlan</p>
	Challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Disparate local policies and stakeholders leading to a lack of Integrated policies • Provision of basic services: Lack of electricity, waste management, potable water to all residents • Support to producers: limited provision of technical and material assistance to producers and agri-food project leaders, linkages and awareness raising • Governance: Organising markets
	Existing Assessments, Policies, Strategies and Initiatives	<p>Assessments</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maps of economic activities of the city (2015) <p>Policies and Strategies</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • City Master Plan (2015), but the food component is missing. <p>Initiatives</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fairtrade town campaign (2015) • ADB Projet de Développement des Chaînes de Valeurs Agricoles (2016) • WFP Plan stratégique pour le Cameroun (2022) • WB Projet d'urgence de lutte contre la crise alimentaire (2022)
	Established Food Policy Network	No
	Stakeholder Mapping and Baseline Assessment Priorities	<p>In this first phase, Ebolowa wants to focus on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mapping specific food related actors and power dynamics between them, in addition to Identifying additional stakeholders • Developing an action plan • Creating a food policy and strategy inventory focusing on impacts on city-region level by reviewing existing policies and local implementation
eThekwini	FoodCLIC Process Goals	<p>Building blocks for the design, facilitation and creation of a Multi-Stakeholder Platform/Reference Group/Food Policy Council</p> <p>Supporting the development of eThekwini Food Strategy</p>

		#FoodPolicyCouncil #FoodStrategy #FoodSecurity #Affordability #Nutrition #HorizontalIntegration
	Challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Food insecurity and Health: Food affordability, malnutrition, childhood stunting ● Lack of coordination and horizontal integration, such as with city health departments for more cohesive messaging with external stakeholders
	Existing Assessments, Policies, Strategies and Initiatives	<p>Assessments</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Stakeholder mapping (2023) ● Inventory of food policies and strategies (2023): readily available online and through FoodCLIC's resources and MUFPP. ● City-region food systems mapping (2023) limited to municipal government support ● Demographic mapping related to food vulnerability/insecurity (2023) <p>Policies and Strategies</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Durban Climate Change Strategy (2015)
	Established Food Policy Network	No
	Stakeholder Mapping and Baseline Assessment Priorities	<p>In this first phase, eThekweni wants to focus on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Mapping stakeholders in the food system value-chain (food distribution, food processing, food consumption, food waste and recovery, food policies) as the present mapping is limited to agricultural producers only ● Understanding power dynamics between government (policy and regulations) and private sector (Production, Distribution and Consumption) ● Strengthening linkages and collaboration between different actors and departments in eThekweni ● Mapping food policies
Fort Portal	FoodCLIC Process Goals	<p>Building blocks for input into a draft food safety ordinance</p> <p>#StakeholderEngagement #FoodSafety</p>
	Challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Health: Food safety & sanitation at food processing points, unregulated informal street food vending with limited funding on infrastructure; ● Weak enforcement of food laws and policies – low uptake of actions ● Mismatch between dietary diversity on the farm and on the plate ● Infant and child malnutrition- child stunting ● Increasing cases Obesity/overweight - dietary-related diseases ● Food loss and food waste – escalating food insecurity ● Limited and unaffordable urban farming technologies that can enrich urban food production – food market oriented
	Existing Assessments, Policies, Strategies and Initiatives	<p>Assessments</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <u>Food stakeholder mapping</u> (2015) ● Inventory of food policies and strategies (2015): Fort Portal Food Systems Lab (FP-FSL). A research and innovation initiative aimed at strengthening the diversity, sustainability, resilience, and

		<p>connectivity of food systems.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • City-region food systems mapping (2015) • <u>Food diaries: Food choices and dietary patterns among households in Western Uganda</u> <p>Policies, Strategies and Initiatives</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Food strategy (2015): The City, District, Sub-County/Town council Nutrition Action Plans, which influence the food producers to consume what they produce to improve on diets, facilitate the informal street vendors to improve on the workplaces and access better handling facilities, promote food summits and dialogues to utilize evidence to inform policies and practices. • Draft Food Policy
	Established Food Policy Network	Yes (2015). The Coalition of the Willing comprises the Nutrition Coordination Committees, street food vendor and market food vendors association, media, chef alliance, academia, small scale farmers etc. The city identified strengthening food networks as a priority area where they need support from the project, with a focus on developing innovative post-harvest technologies to enhance food production, ensure food safety, and reduce food waste.
	Stakeholder Mapping and Baseline Assessment Priorities	<p>In this first phase, Fort Portal wants to focus on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mapping and documenting current food systems actors in the city, with a focus on food safety. Previous mapping exercises (e.g., food diaries, city-region food system map) were outdated or not focused on food safety. • Identifying power dynamics among stakeholders • Strengthening stakeholder engagement (especially with key representatives such as, health inspectors, councillors, market leaders) through sharing of experiences and conducting site visits to contextualise discussions. • Updating city-region food systems mapping (2015) and assessments related to district challenges including agricultural ecosystem degradation, food and nutrition insecurity, and diet-related diseases, demographic mapping related to food vulnerability/insecurity, food systems activities and food safety issues.
Freiburg	FoodCLIC Process Goals	<p>Re-establishment of the House of Food (food hub)</p> <p>#FoodHub #StakeholderEngagement #SustainabilityClimateChange</p>
	Challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Political dimension of food governance and how to get decision makers commitment for a regional food strategy • State out-of-home care/canteen food • Establishment of the House of Food (HoF)
	Existing Assessments, Policies, Strategies and Initiatives	<p>Assessments</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stakeholder mapping on food-related actors (2021, 2022, 2024) • <u>City-region food systems mapping (2015)</u> • Situation analysis and climate balance sheet for agriculture and nutrition in the region Freiburg (2021) • <u>Legal constraints for sustainable urban-rural relations (2023)</u>

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Environmental analysis for the house of food project (2024) <p>Policies and Strategies</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Food Strategy Preliminary Concept (2023) <u>Sustainability goals of Freiburg (2017)</u> <u>Freiburg climate protection concept (2019)</u>
	Established Food Policy Network	Yes (2018-2019)
	Stakeholder Mapping and Baseline Assessment Priorities	<p>In this first phase, Freiburg wants to focus on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stakeholder mapping and identification of power dynamics Doing an environmental analysis for the House of Food project
Tbilisi	FoodCLIC Process Goals	Laying the groundwork for the creation of a Food Council to help direct the discussion, as there is no existing forum for discussing food issues and bringing stakeholders together
	Challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Limited food security and sustainability policy initiatives Lack of specific food-related policies and broader urban development strategies Insufficient educational programs promoting healthy eating habits and food literacy
	Existing Assessments, Policies, Strategies and Initiatives	<p>Assessments</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> City-regions food systems mapping (2024): The <u>WHO FEEDcities Project</u> evaluated the urban street food environment in Tbilisi, providing insights into food accessibility and vendor networks. Evaluation of Food Loss and Waste in Georgia Baseline Food Safety and Urban Agriculture Study Urban Food Systems Assessment – Towards the SDGs EU-Funded Food Bank Georgia Project (2024) <p>Policies and Strategies</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Law of Georgia on Food Loss and Waste Reduction and Food Donation (2023)
	Established Food Policy Network	No
	Stakeholder Mapping and Baseline Assessment Priorities	<p>In this first phase, Tbilisi focused on ...</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Doing a stakeholder and strategy mapping to gain a better understanding of the food system, issues and stakeholder in the city Engaging food and hospitality businesses, wine associations (around 3000 people) and the government
Thessaloniki	Expectations for FoodCLIC Process	<p>Strengthening and widening FPC/Quadruple Helix and better include business and hospitality sector</p> <p>Updating policy guidelines to include further topics such as urban biodiversity, urban pollinators, integrating the food policy into the climate neutrality strategy and the city climate contract, and turning policy</p>

		<p>guidelines into concrete action plans</p> <p>Deepening the participative work done (from policy guidelines to action planning)</p> <p>#StakeholderCollaboration #FoodPolicy #ClimateChangeBiodiversity #ActionPlanning</p>
	Challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Governance and capacity barriers • Linking food policy with climate neutrality • Increasing citizen and stakeholders' participation
	Existing Assessments, Policies, Strategies and Initiatives	<p>Assessments</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stakeholder mapping (2020) • Inventory of food policies and strategies related to school meals (2024) • Mapping of beneficiaries receiving material support/part of municipal social plate (2024) <p>Policies and Strategies</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Food policy (2023) • Climate Action Plan
	Established Food Policy Network	Yes (2019)
	Stakeholder Mapping and Baseline Assessment Priorities	<p>In this first phase, Thessaloniki wants to focus on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mapping stakeholders from professional associations of food retail businesses (restaurants, hotels, pastry shops, etc.) • Stakeholder engagement and bringing Food Policy Council, food activists, and organic farmers together in a "Slow Food Community"; involving restaurants and hotels; dividing FPC members into working groups by thematic axis • Mapping food environments to addressing mapping gaps related to food waste in the gastronomy/hospitality sector • Data collection for city-region food systems mapping (undefined)
Tirana	FoodCLIC Process Goals	<p>Continuing to engage with stakeholders and laying the foundation for the establishment of the policy council, ensuring its integration within the broader political context (Aspiration: creating a Food Policy Council → however, political elections in June might change their plans)</p> <p>Understanding how various actors will contribute to the development and execution of the roadmap and strategy.</p> <p>Supporting a better distribution of farmers markets within the municipality and increasing the presence of small farmers inside the markets</p> <p>Peer-to-peer exchange: Exchange experiences with other cities that are implementing their own food strategy</p> <p>#FoodPolicyCouncil #StakeholderEngagement #SmallscaleFarmers</p>
	Challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to food and nutrition • Food waste
	Existing Assessments,	<p>Assessments</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stakeholder mapping (2024)

	Policies, Strategies and Initiatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Urban food farmers markets <p>Policies and Strategies</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Food Policy (2024)
	Established Food Policy Network	No
	Stakeholder Mapping and Baseline Assessment Priorities	<p>In this first phase, Tirana wants to focus on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improving the stakeholders mapping and especially their role in the future municipal food council Improving the food waste data at municipal level in order to plan targeted interventions apart awareness campaigns for citizens
Wrocław	FoodCLIC Process Goals	<p>Strengthening stakeholder engagement with a focus on food security and crisis management</p> <p>Engaging food-deprived groups</p> <p>#FoodSystemsResilience #StakeholderEngagement</p>
	Challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Food regulations in strategic documents Food security Financial aspects
	Existing Assessments, Policies, Strategies and Initiatives	<p>Assessments</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Partial Stakeholder Mapping (2023) Power Matrix (2023) Demographic mapping related to population density Potential food self-sufficiency of the City of Wrocław (2023) Analysis of the threats relating to the phenomenon of food terrorism (2024) Caring for groups at the risk of food exclusion (Yearly) <p>Policies and Strategies</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Food Policy Wrocław Strategy 2050
	Established Food Policy Network	No
	Stakeholder Mapping and Baseline Assessment Priorities	<p>In this first phase, Wrocław wants to focus on ...</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Gathering stakeholders (CSO, institutions and other municipalities in the region) to co-map relevant stakeholders and those who are missing and need to be involved in the process Mapping of stakeholders from vulnerable and excluded groups as part of the city's food security with a focus on identifying power dynamics among them

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